

UNDERPIN

DATA SPACE FOR MANUFACTURING

Pan-European data space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries

D6.2 Final Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination and Pre-standardisation Plan and Activities Report

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
B2B	Business to Business
CDB	Communication and Dissemination Board
CYS	Cyprus Organization for Standardization
D	Deliverable
DS	Data Space
DSSC	Data Space Support Centre
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LLM	Large Language Model
PM	Project Manager
PR	Press release
SME	Small and Midsize Enterprise
SWC	Semantic Web Company
TP	Tiko PRO
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D6.2 – Final Communication, Dissemination and Pre-Standardisation Plan and Activities Report*, presents a comprehensive overview of the communication and stakeholder engagement efforts carried out under Work Package 6 (WP6) of the UNDERPIN project from December 2023 until November 2025.

UNDERPIN is a project funded under the Digital Europe Programme, focused on designing, deploying, and promoting a secure and sustainable European Data Space for Manufacturing. It aims to enhance predictive maintenance and dynamic asset management across complex industrial environments - specifically within refinery and wind farm sectors. By enabling secure data sharing among large enterprises, SMEs, and technology providers, UNDERPIN contributes to improved operational efficiency, equipment longevity, and circular economy practices in European manufacturing.

This report reflects the full communication and dissemination lifecycle of the project, building on the strategy established in Deliverable D6.1 and evaluating implementation outcomes. It documents how the consortium promoted the vision and technical outcomes of the UNDERPIN Data Space, raised awareness among industrial stakeholders, and built a knowledge-sharing ecosystem around the project's results.

Activities included the development of project identity and branding materials, launch of digital channels (website, social media channels, Zenodo community), publishing of press releases, newsletters, and publications, organisation of events, and conference participation; and collaborations with EU-level initiatives and standardisation bodies.

While some deviations from the initial plan occurred the project successfully achieved most KPIs and exceeded expectations in areas such as scientific publication output and event participation.

2 Introduction

This chapter sets the foundation for the deliverable by outlining its purpose, scope, and connection to other activities within the UNDERPIN project. It provides an overview of how the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement efforts were planned and executed, in alignment with the objectives of Work Package 6 (WP6). Furthermore, it explains the relevance of this deliverable within the broader context of the project and how it supports knowledge transfer, outreach, and long-term impact through coordinated communication actions.

2.1 Purpose of the Document

Deliverable D6.2 Final Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Pre-standardisation Plan and Activities Report serves as the conclusive report of all communication-related actions carried out during the duration of the UNDERPIN project.

The document provides a comprehensive overview of the strategy implementation and the tangible results achieved through communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, branding, and scale-out activities. It evaluates how well the planned actions aligned with actual implementation, identifies key lessons learned, and highlights the tools and channels that proved most effective.

In addition to fulfilling its reporting role, this deliverable is also intended to serve as a practical reference for similar projects. By sharing best practices, successful formats, and effective engagement models, the report can support other EU-funded initiatives in shaping their own communication and stakeholder engagement strategies based on the insights gained through UNDERPIN.

Finally, the document reflects how communication efforts contributed to visibility, knowledge transfer, stakeholder mobilisation, exploitation, and pre-standardisation objectives, while complementing the original strategy defined in D6.1.

2.2 Scope and Structure

This document is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination strategy, actions, and results achieved during the full duration of the UNDERPIN project.

It begins with introductory elements including an overview of WP6. Chapter 3 outlines the strategic planning and implementation logic, summarised planned actions, mechanisms of activity reporting and deviations from the original plan. It also presents monitoring data and an assessment of KPIs. Chapter 4 provides detailed reporting on the various communication and dissemination activities carried out, including website performance, social media, promotional materials, press coverage, newsletters, publications, and use of Zenodo.

Chapter 5 covers community-building efforts such as event participation, organisation of joint events and Road Shows, and the Ambassador Programme. It also highlights collaborations, standardisation-related contributions, and future actions.

Chapter 6 is dedicated to the project's exploitation and continuation strategy, presenting key exploitable results, commercialisation efforts, and the path forward.

Finally, the document concludes with a summary of key insights and supporting annexes.

2.3 Relation to Other Work Packages

Deliverable D6.2 is deeply interconnected with the technical, regulatory, business, and stakeholder-focused work carried out across the UNDERPIN project. While its primary scope lies in communication, dissemination, exploitation, and pre-standardisation, these activities serve as key enablers and multipliers for several other work packages.

The WP2 - *Requirements and Enablers Implementation* defined the foundational requirements and key enablers for the Data Space infrastructure. Effective communication and stakeholder engagement - outlined in this deliverable - were essential for validating these requirements and gathering external feedback, particularly during the Road Show events and survey-based outreach. Similar goes for the WP3 - *Data Space Operational Infrastructure*. The technical development of the UNDERPIN Data Space, led under WP3, benefitted from WP6 through branding alignment, dissemination of progress, and onboarding materials. Communication outputs helped present the infrastructure to stakeholders in a clear, understandable way, while the onboarding portal adopted project visuals and messaging developed under WP6.

The WP6 supported WP4 - *Use Cases for Data Space Demonstration and Validation* by promoting the real-life pilots in the refinery and wind energy domains. Use case outcomes were showcased in newsletters, social media campaigns, Zenodo publications, and Road Show presentations, amplifying their visibility and demonstrating impact.

The WP6 and this deliverable is tightly aligned with WP5 - *Trust Framework, Business Models and Pre-Standardisation*, particularly the business model (D5.1, D5.3) and legal framework (D5.2) activities. Insights gathered through stakeholder engagement helped refine the exploitation strategy, while communication actions supported the scale-out and sustainability objectives. The pre-standardisation was also developed in coordination with WP5, ensuring alignment with EU data governance priorities.

2.4 WP 6 Overview

Work Package 6 (WP6) - *Communication, Dissemination and Scale Out* plays a central role in promoting the UNDERPIN Data Space and generating impact across Europe's manufacturing ecosystem. Its overarching objective is to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and support the population of the Data Space (especially among SMEs) through strategic communication, dissemination, exploitation, and community-building activities.

WP6 focuses on communication and showcasing the technical and business value of joining the UNDERPIN Data Space. By emphasising benefits, this work package positions UNDERPIN as a key enabler of circular economy practices and sustainable industrial innovation.

The work includes targeted actions to engage SMEs and wider stakeholder groups (including clusters, associations, and EU-wide networks) ensuring that UNDERPIN's vision reaches beyond the consortium. Using digital platforms and collaboration with other EU-funded initiatives, WP6 builds synergies to support scale-out and alignment with broader EU digital strategies.

WP6 also contributes to improving public understanding of data sharing and common European data spaces. Through accessible messaging, visual identity, hands-on models, and real-world use case promotion, it fosters trust and practical insight into how data sharing contributes to business efficiency, economic growth, and societal value. Ultimately, WP6 aims to establish a strong, recognisable identity for UNDERPIN and grow a vibrant community of Data Space participants across Europe.

3 Implementation and KPI Summary

This chapter outlines the communication, dissemination, exploitation, and visibility strategy of the UNDERPIN project, as initially defined in Deliverable D6.1, and reports on how these plans were translated into concrete actions throughout the project lifecycle. It assesses the effectiveness and coherence of the communication efforts, while also reflecting on the adaptability of the strategy in response to emerging opportunities and challenges.

The sections that follow revisit the initial objectives and WP6 structure (3.1), define the target audiences (3.2), and present the key planned actions (3.3). A summary of activities carried out is provided in 3.4, while any deviations from the original plan and the reasoning behind them are explained in 3.5. Finally, 3.6 confirms how the project ensured compliance with EU communication and visibility requirements.

This chapter ensures continuity with the original strategy while providing a critical review of its implementation, ultimately demonstrating how communication and stakeholder engagement have contributed to the visibility, understanding, and uptake of the UNDERPIN Data Space.

3.1 Key Planned Activities

The initial Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) outlined a set of strategically designed activities aimed at supporting the visibility, outreach, and stakeholder engagement of the UNDERPIN project. These planned actions were built around clearly defined KPIs and targeted dissemination channels to ensure maximum impact across the European manufacturing ecosystem.

Key planned activities included:

- Development of the UNDERPIN visual identity, including logo, branding guidelines, templates, and visual materials;
- Launch of the official project website as a primary information and dissemination hub;
- Establishment of social media presence, with a particular focus on LinkedIn and YouTube to reach professional audiences and share visual content;
- Creation and distribution of promotional materials, such as flyers, posters, and a roll-up banner for use at events;
- Publication of newsletters to provide regular updates to stakeholders;
- Press releases to communicate major project milestones;
- Publication of scientific and non-scientific articles, including a goal of at least 4 journal publications and 8 conference presentations;
- Participation in external events, including international conferences, workshops, and policy forums;

- Organisation of internal and external project events, including plenary meetings, the Kick-off and Final Conference, technical workshops, webinars, and a UNDERPIN Road Show events;
- Community building initiatives, such as the Ambassador Programme and clustering with complementary initiatives;
- Stakeholder engagement, including outreach to SMEs, digital innovation hubs, standardisation bodies, and related EU-funded projects;
- Monitoring and reporting on KPIs, to evaluate the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities.

All these activities were aligned with the project's strategic goal to populate and promote the UNDERPIN Data Space, foster cross-organisational collaboration, and enable a sustainable and scalable approach to data-driven asset management in the manufacturing sector.

3.2 Activity Reporting

Throughout the duration of the UNDERPIN project, communication and dissemination activities were continuously monitored, documented, and evaluated to ensure alignment with the objectives and KPIs defined in WP6 and Deliverable D6.1. This chapter summarises how the reporting of these activities was structured and what methods were used to collect and categorise the data.

To ensure transparency and consistency, each partner was asked to contribute regularly to internal CD Reporting Table, a structured Excel template designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative outputs. This template was hosted in a shared workspace and included categories such as type of activity (events, publications), dissemination channel (website, social media, newsletter), date of activity, audience reached (number and type), partner responsible, and any supporting links or materials.

The reporting covered all major communication and dissemination actions, including:

- Organisation of events
- Participation in events
- PR & Publications (scientific papers, articles, media mentions)
- Social media
- Website (partners` channels)
- Cooperations
- UNDERPIN channels
- Other

The reporting has been done every six months, and the reviews of the reported activities were conducted within the WP6 team and shared during regular consortium meetings. These insights were used to fine-tune the strategy in real-time, evaluate progress against KPIs, and support interim and final reporting obligations.

In addition to partner contributions, website analytics, social media insights, and newsletter metrics were regularly collected to assess audience engagement and visibility impact. These external indicators helped validate the relevance and reach of the consortium's communication efforts.

Overall, the structured approach to activity reporting allowed the project to maintain a high level of coordination across partners, track impact over time, and ensure that communication and dissemination remained closely aligned with project goals and stakeholder expectations.

3.3 Key Performance Indicators Overview and Achievement

As explained in the *D6.1 Integrated Communication and Dissemination Plan (initial design)*, effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan was evaluated by reaching specified targets for a range of key indicators. This chapter shows reached KPIs (Table 1) and explains achievements.

As explained in Chapter 3.4.1 *Surveys at Major Events*, the originally planned surveys for major industry events were not conducted due to logistical limitations. Instead, the project shifted its focus to gathering feedback during the UNDERPIN Road Show events, as detailed in Chapter 5.4.2 *Surveys*. Additionally, statistics for the UNDERPIN onboarding portal are not available due to the absence of new user registrations during the reporting period (see Chapter 3.4.2 *UNDERPIN Portal – Lack of Usage Data*).

Despite these deviations, the key KPIs and statistics outlined in this deliverable demonstrate that the communication and dissemination efforts effectively brought visibility to the project and contributed to community building and collaboration. All KPIs are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 UNDERPIN` s KPIs

Channel	KPI	Method of measurement	Threshold	Achievement
Events – Up to 25 participants	Number of events	Manually, Reporting	>=4	10
	Number of audience contacts	Surveys	At least 50% of the participants	Road show surveys conducted (chapter 6.4.2)
	Number of participants Interested on UNDERPIN project	Surveys	At least 40% of the participants	

Channel	KPI	Method of measurement	Threshold	Achievement
Events – 25-100 participants	Number of events	Manually	>=2	20
	Number of audience contacts	Surveys	At least 30% of the participants	Road show surveys conducted (chapter 6.4.2)
	Number of participants interested on UNDERPIN project	Surveys	At least 20% of the participants	
Events – more than 100 participants	Number of events	Manually	>=2	10
	Number of participants for UNDERPIN section contacted	Surveys	At least 50% of the participants	
	Number of participants for UNDERPIN section interested in the project	Surveys	At least 40% of the participants	
Journal publications	Number of journal publications by UNDERPIN partners	Direct reporting	>=4	12
Presentations in International Conferences	Number of conference presentations by UNDERPIN partners (persons involved)	Direct reporting	>=8	17
UNDERPIN website	Number of visitors per year	Google Analytics	>=500	Total: 1800+
UNDERPIN portal	Number of the portal visitors per year	Google Analytics	>=500	/
LinkedIn	Number of followers	LinkedIn	>=600	652
	View of UNDERPIN profile	LinkedIn	>=5000	1500+ 1400+ (LinkedIn newsletter)
YouTube	Number of subscribers	You Tube	>=50	26

Project partners focused on disseminating results to the industry by actively participating in key events and preparing scientific publications. The initial KPI target of four papers was significantly exceeded, with a total of 12 papers published. Instead of the eight planned events, the project's partners participated in and organised a total of 40 events.

The official YouTube channel UNDERPIN Project was not intended to grow a large follower base; the focus was on video views and engagement. In total, the channel reached 637 video views with 18.4 total watch hours.

The KPI target for 5,000 views of the UNDERPIN profile was not met. However, considering the industry-specific context and other supporting indicators, the overall objectives of the communication and dissemination activities were successfully achieved. The LinkedIn project profile accumulated over 1,500 views, and additional efforts through the LinkedIn Newsletter (with 12 editions published) attracted more than 1,400 views.

3.4 Deviations from Original Plan and Justifications

During the implementation of WP6, several deviations from the original communication and dissemination plan (as outlined in D6.1) occurred. These changes were driven by practical challenges, market conditions, and the evolving nature of stakeholder engagement. This section outlines the main deviations and provides justifications for each.

3.4.1 Surveys at Major Events

Although the original plan anticipated the implementation of surveys at major industry and stakeholder events to collect feedback and assess awareness, this approach proved unfeasible. Logistical limitations and the nature of external events made it difficult to implement consistent survey distribution. Instead, the project focused on conducting surveys during the UNDERPIN Road Show events and distributing them via QR codes embedded in PowerPoint presentations and printed flyers. This alternative method enabled collection of feedback from a relevant audience in a more controlled setting.

3.4.2 UNDERPIN Portal - Lack of Usage Data

Statistics for the UNDERPIN onboarding portal were not available due to the absence of new user registrations during the reporting period. Given that UNDERPIN is a two-year project, it would be reasonable to expect more meaningful usage data to emerge in the third year when exploitation and onboarding activities would be more appropriate for the project life cycle. While the portal infrastructure was in place, its active use depended on broader stakeholder adoption, which is yet to happen.

3.4.3 Website Developed Beyond Initial Scope

Initially envisioned as a basic project dissemination tool, the UNDERPIN website was significantly expanded during implementation. In addition to standard project information, it included the launch of the "UNDERPIN Edu" subpage, which provided accessible educational content to support stakeholder understanding of Data Spaces. This expansion directly supported capacity building and SME engagement, and contributed to the project's long-term visibility.

3.4.4 Shift in Social Media Strategy – Facebook Deprioritised

Facebook was initially activated as a communication channel, but was deprioritised during the project after limited engagement. Analytics and audience feedback indicated that Facebook did not resonate with the professional and industrial stakeholders that UNDERPIN aimed to reach. As a result, efforts were redirected to LinkedIn, which consistently demonstrated higher

interaction rates and better alignment with the target audience. Nevertheless, all available statistics for this social media is also included in this document.

3.4.5 Road Show Events – Lower Number Than Planned

The original communication plan proposed the organisation of up to 10 Road Show events across Europe. In the end, three in-person events were successfully held - in Athens, Maribor, and Vienna. Organising international Road Shows proved more complex than anticipated, particularly in countries without strong local partner involvement. Challenges included finding a reliable partner (or event organiser), securing venues, attracting attendees, and coordinating logistics. For a still-emerging topic like Data Spaces, additional time and dedicated partnerships would have been necessary to successfully execute the full series of events. We would expect more collaboration and cooperation for organisations connected with this topic.

Despite these deviations, the consortium maintained a flexible and adaptive approach, ensuring that the core objectives of WP6 were met. Alternative strategies were developed where needed, and resources were redirected to channels and activities that delivered the highest impact. These adjustments demonstrate the consortium’s ability to respond pragmatically to evolving project conditions while upholding the overall aims of communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement.

3.5 EU Communication & Visibility Compliance

Throughout the project, all communication, dissemination, and promotional materials produced under UNDERPIN have fully adhered to the EU’s communication and visibility requirements. As outlined in Chapter 2.6 of Deliverable D6.1, every publication, presentation, and digital output prominently featured the EU emblem and included the required funding acknowledgement statement.

Figure 1 Newsletter footer

This compliance extended to all project deliverables, web content, social media posts, newsletters, presentations, and event materials. The EU emblem was used correctly and prominently in accordance with official guidelines, reinforcing the visibility of EU funding and ensuring that all audiences recognised the Union's financial support behind the UNDERPIN initiative.

4 Communication and Dissemination Activity Reporting

This chapter provides a detailed overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the UNDERPIN project. It documents how the strategy outlined in D6.1 was implemented in practice across multiple channels and formats, including branding, website development, social media, promotional materials, media outreach, newsletters, open-access platforms, and scientific publications. The chapter highlights the tools used, engagement achieved, and materials produced to raise awareness, support stakeholder onboarding, and enhance visibility of the UNDERPIN Data Space across Europe.

4.1 Project Branding and Visibility

Throughout the project, a consistent and recognisable visual identity was maintained across all communication and dissemination activities, as initially defined in Chapter 3.1 of Deliverable D6.1. The UNDERPIN branding (comprising logo, colour scheme, typography, and visual assets) was applied systematically across all materials, ensuring coherence, professionalism, and visibility.

This branding was embedded in a wide range of outputs including the project website, social media graphics, event presentations, newsletters, public deliverables, promotional visuals, and partner communication channels. The consistent application of the visual identity contributed to building strong project recognition among stakeholders and across EU-wide communication networks.

The branding framework also served as the basis for the UNDERPIN onboarding page (portal), helping to ensure a seamless visual transition from general project communication to technical user engagement environments. All partners adhered to the branding guidelines, reinforcing a unified image of the project and supporting its long-term visibility and trustworthiness within the European Data Space ecosystem.

Set of visual assets and elements used on digital channels is available in ANNEX I.

4.2 Website and Analytics

The UNDERPIN project website (www.underpinproject.eu) served as the central digital touchpoint for disseminating information, engaging stakeholders, and increasing awareness of the project. As foreseen in D6.1 *Integrated Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (initial design)*, the website is both a dissemination hub and a practical entry point into the UNDERPIN Data Space, serving as a foundation for outreach, onboarding, and communication activities.

Built in line with the project's visual identity and communication goals, the website offers intuitive navigation and accessible content tailored to technical audience (Figure 2). Understanding that the data spaces are novelty, an education part of the website was created, supporting also non-technical audiences (focusing on SMEs).

Figure 2 Project Home page

During the two years of the project, the website was continuously update and its structure change accordingly. At this point, the website structure includes:

- Homepage that introduces the project vision and provides immediate access to the latest updates, while subpages explain the basic information about the project
- About includes
 - UNDERPIN Data Space Value Proposition
 - Use Cases
 - Work Packages
 - Consortium
- News
- Results - not originally foreseen in D6.1, but now implemented, are new subpages such as
 - Events – list of events that partners organised or attended
 - Deliverables – publicly available documents (shared via ZENODO community)
 - Publications – scientific publications and papers accepted at the conferences with links to the documents
 - Promo materials – materials for download
 - Underpin EDU – educational material for better understanding data spaces

The website's design follows all branding and visibility guidelines specified in WP6 and D6.1, including consistent use of fonts, colours, the UNDERPIN logo, and the required EU emblem and

funding disclaimer. GDPR-compliant features such as cookie consent and a privacy policy are also in place, along with a contact form that enables communication with external stakeholders.

Beyond initial expectations, several additional features were introduced during the project. This goes for educational content introduced as **UNDERPIN EDU campaign** that was hosted directly on the website, reinforcing its role in capacity building and awareness and multimedia content, such as videos and campaign visuals that were created and shared via website and social media channels.

A Google Analytics dashboard was set up early in the project to track user interaction. Metrics show:

- Over 1.800 visitors in total,
- Over 18.000 (website) events,
- 53% of visitors came directly to the website (knowing the destination of the project website) – this is outcome of the direct contacts and presentations, links provided on the leaflets, and obviously excellent work of project partners,
- 26% visitors is a result of referral links (16% visitors came via the website of the European Commission digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu which confirms the value of this source; over 5% of the visitors used referral links on the website of project partners – this also proves that the active engagement of the project partners directly contribute to the project visibility),
- 19% of visitors found the website organic (search, social, video) – this activity is a direct outcome of the SEO actions, activities on social media and similar,
- Among the top seven countries, the majority of active users come from Greece, Slovenia, and Austria, reflecting the outreach efforts of the consortium (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Active users per country – top 7 countries

Analytics also show (Figure 4), 64.9% of users accessed the website via desktop, 34.9% via mobile, and only 0.2% via tablets. This distribution suggests that most users are engaging with the content in a professional or office-based setting. This is consistent with our target audience of industry stakeholders, SMEs, and researchers. The notable mobile usage also highlights the importance of maintaining responsive design to support accessibility across devices. (This is not the case with website associated with general public or social media profiles.)

Figure 4 Active users by device category

In conclusion, the UNDERPIN website has gone beyond its initial planning in D6.1. It evolved into a data space hub that not only supports project visibility and outreach but also serves as an entry point into the Data Space and onboarding activities. With its scalable structure and strong branding, the site is well-positioned to continue supporting stakeholder engagement even beyond the project's duration.

4.3 Social Media

In the deliverable D6.1, social media was defined and identified as an important component of UNDERPIN's communication and dissemination strategy. The goal was to reach diverse stakeholder groups, raise awareness about the project's vision, disseminate project outcomes, and contribute to the broader conversation on Data Spaces, predictive maintenance, and digital transformation in manufacturing. The official UNDERPIN social media presence was established on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook and YouTube.

LinkedIn emerged as the primary communication platform for the project. As a professional network with strong reach in the tech, research, and industrial sectors, it provided an ideal environment for reaching SMEs, large companies, clusters, associations, and EU policymakers. Content posted on LinkedIn profile [UNDERPIN project](#) included event announcements, updates on project milestones, dissemination of educational content (e.g., the UNDERPIN EDU campaign), public deliverables, and articles.

In addition, LinkedIn served as the platform for the [UNDERPIN Data Space Newsletter](#), which helped build a loyal subscriber base and regularly engage followers with curated content. This strategic use of the platform ensured consistency, professional outreach, and sustained audience growth.

While the project maintained an account on **X (Twitter)** – [UNDERPIN project](#), its use was limited and complementary. The platform's evolving features and reduced engagement for non-paid

content made it less attractive for regular communication. As a result, content on X was shared selectively, often mirroring LinkedIn posts or being used for tagging event participants and visibility during conferences.

An official **YouTube channel** [UNDERPIN project](#) was launched to host educational videos, particularly for the "UNDERPIN EDU" campaign. The platform allowed the project to deliver visual, accessible explanations about Data Spaces, use cases, and benefits for SMEs (Figure 5). All videos were embedded in the official project website and actively promoted through social media channels.

Figure 5 YouTube channel with overview of the shared videos

4.3.1 Facebook - Early Use and Strategic Withdrawal

Although the project initially created a Facebook channel [UNDERPIN Project](#), it was intentionally phased out during the second year. Facebook did not meet expectations in terms of engagement or visibility among the target groups. As the platform prioritizes personal and entertainment content, it proved less effective for B2B and research-oriented outreach. Furthermore, analytics and partner feedback confirmed significantly higher stakeholder interaction on LinkedIn, leading to the decision to focus resources on more effective channels.

4.3.2 Comparison with Similar Projects

In comparing UNDERPIN's social media approach with other Horizon Europe and Digital Europe initiatives, the strategy aligns with the dominant trend of prioritizing LinkedIn as the lead communication channel. Similar projects also focus on LinkedIn and YouTube, with very limited activity on X and no presence on Facebook. UNDERPIN's use of a LinkedIn newsletter and embedded educational content via YouTube offers a strong example of multichannel outreach focused on professional audiences.

4.3.3 Engagement and Reach Statistics

The UNDERPIN project's social media strategy aligned with current best practices for EU digital innovation projects. By focusing on platforms that support professional communication, content dissemination, and community building, the project ensured targeted outreach and maximised visibility among relevant stakeholders. The prioritisation of LinkedIn and YouTube allowed the team to deliver meaningful, industry-relevant content to the right audiences, while avoiding ineffective or outdated channels such as Facebook.

The table below (Table 2) shows statistic for each of the social media channels that were used for communication and dissemination.

Social Media Channel	Statistic	Results
LinkedIn	Followers	651
	Number of posts	122
	Impressions	68.336
	Article views	1187
LinkedIn Newsletter	Subscribers	295
	Number of articles	12
	Total article views	1501
	Average engagement rate	12.37%
	Average email open rate	33.63%
YouTube	Subscribers	26
	Number of videos	23
	Impressions	12.200
	Watch time (hours)	18.4
	Views	637
X platform	Number of followers	39
	Number of posts	73
Facebook	Number of followers	18
	Number Posts	64
	Views (videos)	117
	Reach	1828

Table 2 Social media statistics

This strategic focus contributed to the project's strong digital footprint and supported the overall goal of promoting the UNDERPIN Data Space and Data Space concept across Europe's manufacturing and innovation landscape.

A table with all post published via project`s channels is available in ANNEX II.

Additional numbers to these statistics are numbers provided by partners. Consortium partners supported project with 92+ mentions on the social media channels. A list of all posts is available in ANNEX V.

4.4 Promotional Materials

As per plan, a variety of promotional materials were developed during the project to support awareness and visibility at events, partner presentations, and stakeholder meetings (roadshows). These materials played a vital role in reinforcing the project’s visual identity and helping to convey the core messages of the UNDERPIN Data Space.

Several flyers were produced in both A5 and folded (American) formats. These were distributed in digital form and in print format where physical presence was required - particularly during road shows and external events. For the road show events, the QR code to the survey was added (Figure 6).

In addition to the flyers, the project produced posters (Figure 7), a project roll-up banner (Figure 8), and branded templates for partner presentations. These materials adhered to the established visual identity guidelines and were used consistently across the consortium. All digital materials are available at the project website ([promo materials](#)).

Partners developed additional promotional items (Figure 8) to support their participation in industry fairs, exhibitions, and workshops. These included custom-branded materials such as pens, bags... Such items were useful for expanding the project’s visibility and leaving a tangible reminder.

All promotional materials, whether centralised or partner-specific, were aligned with the project branding strategy outlined in D6.1 and were designed to ensure professional, coherent, and EU-compliant outreach.

Figure 7 Poster

Figure 6 Flyer A5 with the survey QR code

Figure 8 Examples of promo materials (roll up, USB, bag)

4.5 Press Releases and Media Mentions

Press releases were designed to highlight key project milestones, achievements, and events. Their purpose was to inform both the general public and targeted stakeholders, while increasing project visibility in the wider research, industrial, and policy communities.

Each news was disseminated across partners' own channels. This ensured wide distribution via websites, newsletters, social media platforms, and press networks at local, regional, national, and EU levels. Partners were encouraged to adapt the content to their local context, including translations, to maximize relevance and outreach.

Subsequent press releases covered major project milestones and achievements, Road Show events across Europe, scientific contributions and collaborations with similar initiatives.

The project committed to issuing a minimum of six press releases during its lifetime. Up to the final event, 10 press releases were issued and published at the project website:

1. [Marking the Launch of the UNDERPIN Project](#)
2. [UNDERPIN project in the new Data Spaces Radar Report](#)
3. [UNDERPIN project presented at Data Space Symposium 2024](#)
4. [The First General Assembly of the UNDERPIN project](#)
5. [UNDERPIN at the Semantic Interoperability Workshop and EBDVF 2024](#)
6. [UNDERPIN's Second General Assembly in Vienna](#)

7. [UNDERPIN Presented at ADMA TranS4MErs Final Event in Brussels](#)
8. [The 1st UNDERPIN Roadshow held in Athens](#)
9. [UNDERPIN`s 3rd General Assembly and the Road Show in Maribor](#)
10. [UNDERPIN Showcased at AI Connected Business World 2025 in Athens](#)

Through these efforts and development of additional communication materials, UNDERPIN achieved media mentions in sectoral outlets, partner organization channels, and professional networks. Coverage extended beyond the project’s own platforms, with several mentions in industry newsletters, association bulletins, and partner press releases that targeted SMEs, manufacturing stakeholders, and policy circles. A complete list of all media mentions can be found in Annex III and Annex IV, along with the screen shots of some of the mentions.

4.6 Newsletters

The UNDERPIN Newsletter was established as a recurring communication tool to keep stakeholders informed about the project’s progress. The aim was to provide concise and accessible updates on developments, achievements, and events, supplementing other dissemination activities such as social media and the project website.

The newsletter was distributed primarily through LinkedIn Newsletter option (via a dedicated project channel), ensuring GDPR compliance and easy subscription. In parallel, efforts were made to expand outreach by encouraging subscriptions through the project website and contributions from consortium partners. A more industry oriented and technical articles were prepared in collaboration with project partners, ensuring that all technical and strategic areas of the project were represented.

Over the two years of the project, a total of 12 newsletter issues were published under the channel name *UNDERPIN Data Space* on LinkedIn (Table 3).

The newsletters featured a mix of content, including announcements of events and project milestones, dataspace-oriented topics as part of the educational campaign outputs and external collaborations.

By the end of the project, the newsletter had in total:

Subscribers	295
Number of issues	12
Total article views	1501
Total articles impressions	6680
Average engagement rate	12.37%
Average email open rate	33.63%

Table 3 LinkedIn Newsletter statistics

The average email open rate for UNDERPIN newsletters reached 33.63%, which is considered significantly above industry norms. For most sectors, a successful open rate typically ranges

between 15% and 25%¹., with an overall benchmark of 20–30% depending on the industry. UNDERPIN’s consistently higher engagement suggests strong interest and relevance among its target audience, indicating the effectiveness of the project’s content and dissemination strategy.

The list of all newsletter and individual statistics is available in the Table 4 *Statistics for each newsletter issue* (below).

¹ S. Lawrence: How to Track An Email Marketing Open Rate Average; Source:
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-track-email-marketing-open-rate-average-stein-lawrence-8tk5e/>

Table explanation: IM – impressions, R – reach, V – views, ER – engagement rate, OR – (email) open rate; NA – not available

Table 4 Statistic for each newsletter issue

	Publishing date	Newsletter title	Link	IM	R	V	ER	OR
1	4.7.2024	Introduction to Data Spaces	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/introduction-data-spaces-underpinproject-0zkof/	31	10	28	25%	NA
2	7.8.2024	Benefits and Challenges of Data Spaces	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/benefits-challenges-data-spaces-underpinproject-u64if/	346	230	86	36.4%	30%
3	3.9.2024	Predictive Maintenance: Revolutionizing Equipment Care	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/predictive-maintenance-revolutionizing-equipment-care-sdchf/	383	221	117	23.9%	42%
4	17.9.2024	Predictive Maintenance + UNDERPIN Data Space	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/predictive-maintenance-underpin-data-space-underpinproject-ealrf/	449	245	100	8.2%	32%
5	18.11.2024	UNDERPIN's Second General Assembly in Vienna	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/underpins-third-general-assembly-vienna-underpinproject-shwlf/	1797	1010	268	7.7%	41%
6	23.12.2024	Key Takeaways of the UNDERPIN's First Roadshow in Athens	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/key-takeaways-underpins-first-roadshow-athens-underpinproject-41abc/	611	303	151	7.1%	38%
7	1.4.2025	The Role of Data Spaces in Advancing the EU's Clean Industrial Deal	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/role-data-spaces-advancing-eus-clean-industrial-deal-xdckf/	392	240	138	6.6%	39%
8	23.4.2025	Join Us for the SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dives	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/join-us-sm4rt-underpin-deep-dives-underpinproject-zk1ef/	556	290	155	6.7%	35%
9	25.4.2025	Join Us at the UNDERPIN Road Show in Maribor	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/join-us-underpin-road-show-maribor-underpinproject-hwmif/	607	264	109	7.4%	30%

	Publishing date	Newsletter title	Link	IM	R	V	ER	OR
10	28.5.2025	UNDERPIN` s 3rd General Assembly and the Road Show in Maribor	www.linkedin.com/pulse/underpins-3rd-general-assembly-road-show-maribor-underpinproject-nvoaf/	547	290	127	6.7%	30%
11	24.7.2025	Join Us in Vienna to Discover Manufacturing Data Spaces	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/join-us-vienna-discover-manufacturing-data-spaces-underpinproject-zb69f	848	529	109	4.3%	30%
12	15.9.2025	The 3rd Road Show in Vienna: Bringing Data Spaces Closer to Industry	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/3rd-road-show-vienna-bringing-data-spaces-closer-industry-useof	553	363	87	8.7%	23%
			TOTAL	7120	3995	1475	12.39%	34.7%

The newsletter will continue beyond the official end of the project, with a final issue summarizing results and achievements. This ensures that stakeholders remain connected to the project’s outcomes and that the UNDERPIN community sustains momentum in the post-project phase.

4.7 Zenodo

During the implementation of the UNDERPIN project, the consortium identified Zenodo as a valuable dissemination platform, even though it had not been included in the original communication strategy. Zenodo, developed by OpenAIRE and hosted by CERN, is an open-access repository that enables projects and researchers to freely share and preserve publications, datasets, and other outputs.

The platform supports persistent identifiers (DOIs), flexible licensing, and compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), making it a trusted and sustainable environment for open science.

Recognizing these benefits, the project created an official UNDERPIN Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/underpin>). This dedicated space served as a digital library for all publicly available outputs, ensuring visibility beyond the project website and initial dissemination channels.

The repository hosted a diverse range of materials, addressing both scientific and industrial audiences. The impact of using Zenodo was measurable. By the end of the project, the UNDERPIN Zenodo community contained materials, views and downloads as shown in the table below (Table 5).

Table 5 Zenodo community statistics

Type of the Material		Quantity	Views	Downloads
Scientific papers	Peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers (in open-access form)	11	386	220
Public deliverables	Technical reports, white papers, and case studies approved for dissemination	6	3	3
Presentations	Slide decks and posters from conferences, workshops, and project events	2	47	27
Press and outreach materials	Press releases, newsletters, and other communication outputs	1	2	4
	Total	19	438	254

These statistics provided valuable insights into which materials attracted the most attention, supporting continuous improvement in dissemination strategies.

The Zenodo community significantly enhanced the long-term accessibility and visibility of UNDERPIN results. It created a permanent archive of knowledge outputs that will remain available to stakeholders long after the project's conclusion. By providing a single, trusted repository, Zenodo amplified the project's reach among both research and industry audiences,

helping to attract interest from communities that traditional dissemination alone may not have reached.

4.8 Publications

Scientific and public dissemination through publications has been an important element of UNDERPIN's communication and knowledge-sharing strategy.

Over the course of the project, the consortium successfully published 12 scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals and conferences, ensuring that project results reached both the academic community and industry stakeholders. These papers reflect the technical depth of the project and contribute to advancing the state of the art in data spaces, predictive maintenance, semantics and manufacturing digitalization.

In addition, the project made 3 presentations and 6 public deliverables openly accessible, further supporting transparency and stakeholder engagement. The deliverables provided practical insights into regulatory frameworks, business models, communication strategies, and technical implementation. Looking beyond the official project duration, 3 additional public deliverables are planned for publication, continuing to expand the project's impact and ensuring long-term accessibility of results. Other publications include: data sets and keynote presentations.

Together, these publications showcase UNDERPIN's commitment to open science, compliance with FAIR principles, and broad dissemination of results to both the research and business communities.

A full list of scientific papers and public deliverables is provided in the table below (Table 6).

Table 6 List of publications (papers, presentations, deliverables)

No	Title of the Publication		Download Link
1	Adapting Ontology-Based Data Access for Data Spaces	Presented at the 2 nd International Workshop on Semantics in Dataspaces, May 2024, Crete (Greece).	https://zenodo.org/records/17063368
2	Raising the Role of Vocabulary Hubs for Semantic Data Interoperability in Dataspaces	Presented at the 3 rd Workshop on Semantic Interoperability in data spaces, Oct 1st, 2024.	https://zenodo.org/records/17047518
3	MOXAI – Manufacturing Optimization through Model-Agnostic Explainable AI and Data-Driven Process Tuning	Proceedings of the 8th European Conference of the Prognostics and Health Management Society 2024	https://zenodo.org/records/15775516
4	Semantic Problems in Data Spaces	AIOTI Workshop on Semantic Interoperability for Digital Twins, 5-6 February 2025, Sophia Antipolis, France	https://zenodo.org/records/17047444
5	Using LLM to Generate In-Depth Column Descriptors in the UNDERPIN Manufacturing/Maintenance Dataspace	Keynote presentation Workshop: Large Language Models to support semantic interoperability (Interoperable Europe, SEMIC and BDVA)	https://zenodo.org/records/17045724
6	Six-Month Monitoring Dataset from a 10-Turbine Onshore Wind Farm in Greece (SMD10TOWFGR)	Paper publication: IEEE Xplore	https://zenodo.org/records/15781269 https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11017466
7	Six-Month Monitoring Dataset from a 10-Turbine Onshore Wind Farm in Greece	Data Set - A sample of wind farm turbine generator data from the UNDERPIN data space	https://zenodo.org/records/14546480
8	Predictive Maintenance for Wind Turbines: Leveraging Sensor Data with Traditional and Novel Machine-Learning Techniques	Paper presentation at the 6th Interdisciplinary Data Science Conference (IDSC)	https://underpinproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/IDSC_2025_PMWF_camre.pdf
9	Federated Vocabulary Hubs as a Building Block for Semantic Layers in Data Spaces	The 3 rd International Workshop on Semantics in Dataspaces, co-located with the Extended Semantic Web Conference, June 01 – 02, 2025, Portorož, Slovenia	https://zenodo.org/records/17045643

No	Title of the Publication		Download Link
10	Proactive Fault Detection in Wind Turbine Generators using SCADA Measurements	Presented at the 15th Prognostics and System Health Management Conference (PHM 2025) in Bruges, Belgium, June 2–5.	https://zenodo.org/records/16539223
11	Semantically-Enabled Data Spaces for Intelligent Data Asset Discovery	21st International Conference on Semantic Systems (SEMANTICS 25), Vienna, 3-5 September 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/16762447
12	Semantic Representation Challenges in AAS, ECLASS and SAMM	Paper, AIOTI Workshop on Semantic Interoperability for Digital Twins, 5-6 February 2025, Sophia Antipolis, France	https://zenodo.org/records/17047480
13	Semantic Metadata Interoperability for data discovery and analytics in the UNDERPIN Data Space	Presentation at Digital Factory Alliance: SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dive online event	https://zenodo.org/records/17045600
14	Explainable AI for Industrial Predictive Maintenance in the UNDERPIN Manufacturing Dataspace	Paper, SENTIS 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/16778818
15	D2.1 UNDERPIN requirements and enablers adaptation mid-term report, review of relevant regulatory and standardization landscape, plan for implementation of pre-standardization activities	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061874
16	D3.1 UNDERPIN dataspace infrastructure, mid-term deployment and integration report	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061945
17	D4.2 Use Case Validation & Lessons learnt, mid-term and final report	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061986
18	D5.1 Existing business models assessment	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061748
19	D5.2 Trust creation processes design	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061821
20	D6.1 Integrated Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (initial design)	Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/17061571
21	Designing Sustainable Business Models for Data Spaces: Insights from the Manufacturing Sector	Paper publication, Technologies journal, Oct 2025	

5 Community Building Activities

This chapter presents the community engagement efforts undertaken to build awareness, foster collaboration, and encourage participation in the UNDERPIN Data Space. It includes an overview of the project's participation in external events, the organisation of joint Deep Dive webinars, and the coordination of the three Road Show events held in strategic European locations. The chapter also covers the design of the UNDERPIN Ambassador Programme and it highlights relevant collaborations and contributions to standardisation efforts, supporting long-term stakeholder involvement and alignment with broader EU initiatives.

5.1 Participation at Events

Attending and organising events was important activity of UNDERPIN's communication and dissemination strategy, providing direct opportunities to raise visibility, engage with stakeholders, and create cross-sectoral dialogue around the project's objectives. As planned in the original strategy (D6.1), the consortium successfully implemented a multi-layered event approach, which included participation in external conferences, organisation of joint and own-branded events, and regular consortium meetings.

Consortium partners actively participated in 40 events (conferences, meetings, workshops, webinars). These included both technical and thematic events relevant to manufacturing, digital transformation, AI, and Data Spaces. Partners used these platforms to present project results, share lessons learned from the pilot use cases, engage with stakeholders and build synergies with similar EU-funded initiatives. All events are listed in the Table 7.

Table 7 All attended events

N o	DATE	Place	Event title	Type	Level	Role	Partners
1	25.-26.1.2024.	Vienna, Austria	Workshop: Requirements Engineer UNDERPIN	Workshop	European	Organiser, presenter	SWC
2	15.2.2024.	Online	Poduzetnički doručak	Webinar	European	Organiser, presenter	TP
3	12-14.3.2024.	Darmstadt, Germany	Data spaces Symposium (DSSC)	Conference	International	(Participant and presenter)	MOH, INNOV, WM, SWC
4	6.-9.5.2024.	NYC, USA	Knowledge Graph Conference 2024	Conference	International	Participant	SWC
5	22.5.2024.	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Tehnološki park Ljubljana	Workshop	National	Participant, Presenter, Organiser	TP
6	26-30.5.2024.	Crete, Greece	Semantics in Dataspaces	Workshop (offline)	International	Participant and presenter	AIT, SWC
7	31.5.2024.	Brussels, Belgium	DataSpace 4.0 Final Event	Conference	European	Participant and presenter	MOH
8	1-5.7.2024	Prague, Czech Republic	8 th European Conference of the Prognostics and Health Management Society (PHME24)	Conference	International	Participant and presenter	AIT
9	30.9.2024.	Online	IDSA Ecosystem Building Call Industrial Data Spaces in Manufacturing: The UNDERPIN Project	Webinar	International	Participant and presenter	MOH
10	17-19.9.2024.	Amsterdam, Netherlands	SEMANTiCS 2024 Conference	Conference	International	Participant and presenter	SWC

No	DATE	Place	Event title	Type	Level	Role	Partners
11	1.10.2024	Budapest, Hungary	Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces	Workshop (offline)	International	Participant, Organiser, Co-sponsor	INNOV, SWC, OT
12	2-4.10.2024.	Budapest, Hungary	European Big Data Value Forum 2024	Conference	International	Participant, presenter, panel organiser	INNOV, SWC, OT
13	24.10.2024.	Online	October Online Datathlon	Workshop	International	Organiser, presenter	OT
14	26.11.2024.	Athens, Greece	1 st Road Show Event	Workshop	International	Organiser, presenter	MOH, WM
15	28.11.2024.	Brussels, Belgium	ADMA TranS4Mers Final Event	Conference	International	Participant, presenter	TP
16	5.2.2025.	Sophia Antipolis, France	AIOTI Workshop on Semantic Interoperability for Digital Twins	Workshop (offline)	European	Speaker	OT
17	11.2.2025.	Online	Poduzetnički doručak	Webinar	National	Organiser, presenter	TP, MOH
18	11-12.3.2025.	Warsaw, Poland	Data Spaces Symposium	Conference	International	Speaker, participant	HUA, MOH
19	10.4.2025.	Online	Workshop: Large Language Models to support semantic interoperability	Workshop (online)	European	Speaker	OT
20	10.4.2025.	Vienna	DIGITAL Europe Day 2025	Workshop (offline)	National	Participant and presenter,	AIT
21	29.4.2025.	Online	SM4RT-PIN Deep Dive: AI-Driven Predictive Maintenance for Wind	Webinar	International	Organiser, presenter	AIT

No	DATE	Place	Event title	Type	Level	Role	Partners
			Turbines and Refineries Using the UNDERPIN Data Space			Collaboration	
22	30.4.2025.	Online, Greece	TORPEDOES datathon: Teaching factORY datasPacEs DatathOn for wind turbinES	Workshop	National	Organiser, presenter	MOH
23	13.5.2025.	Online	SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dive: Semantic Metadata Interoperability in UNDERPIN Data Space	Webinar	International	Organiser, presenter, collaboration	SWC, OT
24	21.-23.5.2025.	Berlin, Germany	GITEX EUROPE 2025	Conference	International	Participant, exhibitor	TP
25	22.5.2025.	Maribor, Slovenia	2 nd Road Show Event	Workshop	International	Organiser, presenter	TP, all
26	26.05.2025.	Salzburg, Austria	6th Interdisciplinary Data Science Conference (iDSC'25)	Conference	European	Participant and presenter	AIT
27	26.5.2025.	Athens, Greece	IM-X Council Meeting (by International Manufacturing-X)	Others	International	(Participant)	MOH
28	27.5.2025.	Online	SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dive: Data Spaces Business Models in the context of UNDERPIN project use cases	Webinar	International	Organiser, presenter Collaboration	HUA
29	27-28.5.2025.	Athens, Greece	BDVA-Data week	Conference	International	Participant	MOH
30	1-5.6.2025	Portorož, Slovenia	Semantics in Dataspaces	Workshop (offline)	European	Participant, presenter	SWC
31	4.6.2025.	Bruges, Belgium	15th Prognostics and System Health Management Conference (PHM 2025)	Conference	International	Participant, presenter	AIT

No	DATE	Place	Event title	Type	Level	Role	Partners
32	10.6.2025.	Online	SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dive: Digital Product Passport (DPP) applied in energy-related manufacturing industry in UNDERPIN	Webinar	International	Organiser, presenter Collaboration	WM
33	24.6.2025.	Athens, Greece	the 15th AI Connected Business World 2025	Conference	International	Participant and presenter	INNOV
34	9.9.2025.	Vienna, Austria	3 rd Road Show Event	Workshop	International	Organiser, presenter	AIT, SWC, MOH, MORE, TP
35	9.9.2025.	Italy	Alpe Adria Innovation	Conference	European	Participant	TP
36	9.10.2025.	Online	Plattform Industrie 4.0 // Research Insight: UNDERPIN - dynamisches Asset-Management und prädiktive Instandhaltung	Webinar	National	Presenter	AIT, SWC
37	5.11.2025.	Online	Von KI bis eHealth: Die neuen Digital-Europe-Themen im Überblick	Webinar	National	Presenter	AIT
38	20.11.2025.	Online	SM4RT-UNDERPIN Deep Dive: How to achieve market and business value from data-driven innovation	Webinar	International	Organiser, presenter Collaboration	MOH, HUA, AIT, SPH
39	25.11.2025.	Klagenfurt, Austria	Summit Industrie40 2025	Summit	National	Presenter	AIT
40	26.11.2025.	Athens, Greece	GAIA-X event		International	Participant, Coorganizer	MOH, All

5.1.1 Photos and Short Description from the Selected Events

The UNDERPIN project made its first strong and vibrant appearance at the **Data Space Symposium 2024** held in Darmstadt, Germany, on 12-14 March 2024, with active participation from project partners Motor Oil Hellas, Semantic Web Company, Watermelon, and INNOV-ACTS. That year, Data Spaces Symposium, renowned as the premier event on data spaces globally, attracted nearly 1000 attendees from around the world. Hosted by the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) and the Data Spaces Business Alliance (DSBA), this symposium holds significant importance for leaders in data space innovation and strategy. During the second day, as part of the Data Spaces for Manufacturing, Supply Chain, and Logistics session, Mr Panagiotis Georgiou from Motor Oil Hellas (MOH) succinctly outlined the UNDERPIN project actions.

At the **Second International Workshop on Semantics in Dataspaces (SDS)**, co-located with the Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2024), May 26 - 27, 2024, Hersonissos, Greece, our consortium partners AIT and SWC presented their paper *Adapting Ontology-based Data Access for Data Spaces*. The workshop provided an opportunity for networking. One of the outcomes of the workshop is a W3C community group, set up to continue the collaboration. Interesting discussions about Solid, IDS and Gaia-X, and the advancements in the field of dataspaces took place, while the community expressed its interest to follow up in the next event. (Figure 9)

Figure 9 Mrs Medina Andresel from AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, and Mr Robert David from Semantic Web Company, had the privilege of presenting the publication at the 2nd International Workshop on Semantics in Dataspaces, May, Crete.

On May 31, 2024, the **DATASPACE 4.0 Final Event** unfolded in Brussels, Belgium, marking a significant milestone in the journey of the Data Space 4.0 industry community. The event aimed to celebrate this achievement and share the journey and outstanding outcomes, after two years of dedicated work and collaboration by the DATASPACE 4.0 consortium. The event was also a strategic meeting point for CSA partners and an avenue to forge connections. The day was packed with presentations and discussions covering the technical pillars of the data space framework, deployments, and industrial agreements.

A special roundtable titled “Data in Manufacturing, EDIHs, SMEs & Regions” provided a platform for in-depth discussion on pivotal topics. Key speakers, including Mr Aristotelis Ntafalias from MOH, presented the objectives and current status of the UNDERPIN project, enriching the dialogue with their insights (Figure 10). The event also featured a hybrid roundtable, provoking a lively exchange of ideas on manufacturing innovation assets from various perspectives including EDIHs, SMEs, and regions. These discussions underscored the diversity and richness of viewpoints, vital for shaping future directions in manufacturing data spaces.

Figure 10 Mr Aristotelis Ntafalias (Motor Oil Hellas) presenting the UNDERPIN project at DATASPACE 4.0 Final event, May 31, 2024, Brussels

Participation at ADMA TranS4MErs Final Event on November 28, 2025, in Brussels, gave us an opportunity to connect with initiatives that drive manufacturing excellence and Industry 4.0 transformation. Sandra Bortek from Tiko Pro presented the project. (Figure 11)

Figure 11 ADMA TranS4MErs Final Event. Sandra Bortek (middle) from Tiko PRO with the presenters of other projects.

Participation at the **Data Spaces Symposium in Warsaw, March 2025**, included the presentation “UNDERPIN: Revolutionizing Collaboration for European Manufacturers” by Elena Politi from Harokopio University of Athens (Figure 12). Her presentation not only showcased the importance of building a sustainable, interoperable dataspace but also emphasized the transformative potential it holds for European manufacturers. On Day 2 at the Round Table with Start-ups and SMEs: AI Innovation in Data Ecosystems, our partner Vladimir Alexiev from Ontotext participated and shared his expertise on how AI is shaping the future of data spaces.

Figure 12 Elena Politi (Harokopio University of Athens) presenting at Data Spaces Symposium (Warsaw, 11-12 March 2025)

Figure 13 Presentation of the paper "Proactive Fault Detection in Wind Turbine Generators using SCADA Measurements" at the 15th Prognostics and System Health Management Conference (PHM 2025) in Bruges, Belgium, June 2–5.

Project partners also presented UNDERPIN at the **15th AI Connected Business World conference** in Athens, in June, 2025, where innovation, AI, and digital transformation took the spotlight. During the session “Artificial Intelligence: The New Catalyst of the Digital World”, Odysseas Kokkinos from Innov-acts shared how UNDERPIN is driving the future of manufacturing through secure data spaces and predictive maintenance (Figure 14).

Figure 14 AI Connected Business World, Athens, June, 2025

5.2 Joint Events: SM4RT-PIN Deep Dives

In addition to participating in third-party events, UNDERPIN also organised, in collaboration with the SMARETNANCE project, 5 Deep Dives (online webinars). These sessions explored technical and business aspects of Data Spaces in relation to predictive maintenance and dynamic asset management. The list of the webinars follows:

5.2.1 AI-Driven Predictive Maintenance for Wind Turbines and Refineries Using the UNDERPIN

In this session, Axel Weissenfeld (AIT) and Apostolos Garos (SPH) presented the UNDERPIN project and its predictive maintenance use-cases for refineries and wind farms. The session also provided valuable insights into the UNDERPIN Data Space, focusing on the integration of predictive maintenance technologies for model training, near real-time inference, and the services provided to support data processing in predictive maintenance.

Date: 29th April 2025, 12:00 – 12:45 PM CET

Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BoG2Pmz6E3E&t=1s>

5.2.2 Semantic Data Interoperability (SMI) for Data Discovery and Analytics in the UNDERPIN Data Space

Join Petar Ivanov and Vladimir Alexiev from Ontotext discussed how semantic data interoperability can transform data discovery and analytics within the UNDERPIN Data Space, enabling more effective data sharing across industries. The session focused on use-cases in refineries and wind farms.

Date: 13th May 2025, 12:00 - 12:45 PM CET

Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zcRVjL7lX5Y&t=1s>

5.2.3 Data Spaces Business Models in the UNDERPIN Project Use Cases

Elena Politi from Harokopio University of Athens, explored data spaces business models focusing on UNDERPIN use cases in refineries and wind farms.

Date: 27th May 2025, 12:00 - 12:45 PM CET

Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5LCjOhdVgz4>

5.2.4 Digital Product Passport (DPP) Applied in Energy-Related Manufacturing Industry in UNDERPIN

In this session, Giorgos Chrysokentis from Watermelon delved into how the Digital Product Passport (DPP) is being applied within energy-related in the UNDERPIN project, focusing on use-cases aimed at improving sustainability and circularity.

Date: 10th June 2025, 12:00 – 12:45 PM CET

Recording:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9clWreJUX6Q&t=662s>

5.2.5 How to Achieve Market and Business Value from Data Driven Innovation

In the last month of the project, partners organised the 5th event in collaboration with the SM4RTENANCE project. Event included presentations:

- UNDERPIN Project, Aristotelis Ntafalias (MOH), Elena Politie (HUA)
- Smart Predictive Maintenance for Refineries, Axel Weissenfeld (AIT)
- Proactive Fault Detection and Predictive Maintenance System for Wind Turbines, Apostolos Garos (SPH)

Date: 20th November 2025, 10:30 – 12:00 CET

All events were promoted via project`s digital channels as well through partner network.

5.3 Joint Events

5.3.1 TORPEDOES

The TORPEDOES – Data Spaces Datathon was organized in April by UNDERPIN and Flex4Res projects, and powered by EIT Manufacturing South East, Motor Oil and MORE (Motor Oil Renewable Energy).

Figure 15 TORPEDOES banner

The event highlighted both UNDERPIN and FLEX4RES projects, showcasing how European initiatives and the manufacturing sector join forces to boost innovation and collaboration in Europe. Students had an opportunity to tackle a challenge in predictive maintenance for wind farms, using valuable datasets provided by MORE (Motor Oil Renewable Energy). Specifically, the goal was to develop a predictive maintenance model using real-time sensor data from wind turbines, which aims at minimising downtime and maintenance costs, optimise predictive accuracy and create practical, data-driven solutions for real-world wind farm operations, and to optimise predictive accuracy and create practical, data-driven solutions for real-world wind farm operations.

5.3.2 GAIA-X Event – Final Event

On 26 November 2025, UNDERPIN partners joined the GAIA-X event, hosted at the Benaki Museum in Athens (Figure 16). This event brought together two leading EU-funded projects, UNDERPIN and FLEX4RES, both paving the way for the future of data spaces in manufacturing. Event also featured EIT Manufacturing’s major industrial partners, including Motor Oil Hellas (Energy Sector) and SIDENOR (Steel Industry), sharing real-world success stories. This event was also opportunity to celebrate the winners of the TORPEDOES Hackathon, where students tackled predictive maintenance challenges for wind farms using datasets from MORE (Motor Oil Renewable Energy). This event marked the ending of the UNDERPIN project. The partners

attended the event and the promotional materials were shared. Mr Ntalias (MOH) and Mrs Visvardi presented UNDERPIN (Figure 17).

Figure 16 GAIA-X event banner

Figure 17 Mr Ntalias (MOH) and Mrs Visvardi presenting UNDERPIN

5.4 Road Show Events

One of the key components of UNDERPIN's communication, dissemination, and scale-out strategy has been the organization of the roadshow events. These events were planned to bring Data Space concepts and project results directly to industrial stakeholders, fostering real-world dialogue, awareness, and future collaboration.

Road Show events were already foreseen as a strategic activity in *D6.1 – Integrated Communication and Dissemination Plan*, where they were described as a tool to bridge the gap

between technical outputs and user awareness, especially in complex domains such as predictive maintenance and industrial data sharing.

The aims of the event were to:

- Engage targeted stakeholders from the manufacturing, energy, and ICT sectors
- Showcase use cases and demonstrators in real-life settings
- Establish UNDERPIN as a recognisable actor in the EU Data Space ecosystem
- Complement the communication and dissemination efforts with live interaction

These goals have been actively pursued and fulfilled through the following three Road Show events:

1. Athens Road Show – Launch Event

Date: 26 November 2024	Location: Athens, Greece
Overview: The first UNDERPIN Road Show was held in Athens. This event introduced the concept of the UNDERPIN Data Space to stakeholders from the energy, manufacturing, and research sectors. Presentations covered the project vision, objectives, and the strategic role of data sharing in predictive maintenance and dynamic asset management. The session highlighted opportunities for SMEs and established the foundation for UNDERPIN’s stakeholder network. (Figure 18)	
Press release: https://underpinproject.eu/news/the-1st-underpin-roadshow-held-in-athens/ Key Takeaways: https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/key-takeaways-underpins-first-roadshow-athens-underpinproject-41abc/	

Figure 18 Road Show Athens

2. Maribor Road Show – Strengthening Regional Dialogue

Date: 27 May 2025	Location: Maribor, Slovenia
Overview: Organised in conjunction with the project’s third General Assembly, the Maribor Road Show focused on regional engagement and the role of Data Spaces in fostering cross-border innovation in manufacturing. It showcased the real-world benefits of the UNDERPIN Data	

Space for SMEs and industry stakeholders, with a strong emphasis on usability, scalability, and sustainability. The event featured live demonstrations and discussions on pilot use cases from the refinery and wind energy sectors. (Figure 19)

Press release: <https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpins-3rd-general-assembly-and-the-road-show-in-maribor/>

Mentions:

- **TP:** <https://www.tiko-pro.hr/pretrazivac/tiko-pro-ugostio-generalnu-skupstinu-i-road-show-doga%C4%91aj-projekta-underpin-u-mariboru>
- **Industrie 4.0:** <https://plattformindustrie40.at/blog/event/underpin-road-show-discover-the-future-of-data-spaces-in-manufacturing/>
- **DIH Slovenia:** <https://dih slovenia.si/aktualno/dogodki/vabilo-na-mednarodni-dogodek-underpin-road-show-maribor>

Figure 19 Maribor Road Show

3. Vienna Road Show – Engaging the European Industry Hub

Date: 9 September 2025	Location: Vienna Austria
<p>Overview: Co-hosted with support from the Vienna Business Agency, Plattform Industrie 4.0, champi4.0ns project, DataBri-X project, GAIA-X Hub Austria, this event highlighted the impact of data sharing, AI, and Digital Product Passports (DPPs) on manufacturing excellence. Sessions addressed industrial pain points and how UNDERPIN’s infrastructure enables trusted, cross-organisational collaboration. (Figure 20)</p>	
<p>Press release: https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-road-show-vienna-bringing-data-spaces-closer-to-industry/</p> <p>Video announcement: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jXN3l0nrw1U</p>	
<p>Mentions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DATABri-X: https://databri-x.eu/databri-x-supports-underpin-road-show-in-vienna-exploring-data-spaces-and-ai-in-manufacturing/ - European data: https://data.europa.eu/en/news-events/events/underpin-roadshow-exploring-data-spaces-and-ai-manufacturing-excellence - Graphwise: https://graphwise.ai/event/underpin-road-show-in-viennaon-site-event-template-duplicate-me/ 	

Figure 20 Vienna Road Show event visual and announcement at European data portal

The Road Show was designed as a two-and-a-half-hour presentation, workshop, and networking event with a clearly structured agenda. All partners actively contributed to drafting the agenda, which was adjusted each time based on the experience from previous events and feedback from participants. These sessions also served as a valuable testbed to understand which formats and activities would be effective for scaling out Data Spaces in the future.

Each Road Show was hosted in a strategic European location and was either co-located with the project's General Assembly or organised in collaboration with local industry organisations and related initiatives. This ensured a combination of internal project alignment and external stakeholder outreach.

The typical agenda included an introduction to the concept of Data Spaces, an overview of the UNDERPIN Data Space and its benefits, presentation of use cases and the Q&A session. A topic of digital product passport was added as a separate topic as well.

Each event gathered an average of 20 attendees, with over 40 individuals registering per session. The consistent level of participation and the high engagement during discussions – including numerous questions from the audience – clearly demonstrated that Data Spaces are still a relatively novel and unfamiliar concept for many industry stakeholders. However, once introduced to the topic, participants quickly began to understand its relevance and potential. The discussions revealed strong interest, insightful ideas, and a growing awareness of the importance and benefits that Data Spaces can bring to industry transformation. We also anticipated that organising online Road Show events could enhance the project's visibility and raise awareness about the topic, as well as bring more attendees to the event.

5.4.1 Communication Activities for the Road Show Events

The communication strategy for the UNDERPIN Road Show events relied on a multi-channel, collaborative approach to ensure strong visibility, stakeholder engagement, and effective feedback collection. Key activities included:

- Communication via the project’s digital channels - each event was promoted through the UNDERPIN website (dedicated articles), social media platforms (LinkedIn, X/Twitter), and the project’s LinkedIn newsletter.
- Distribution of information via DIHs and media – announcement was shared through Digital Innovation Hubs and relevant media outlets, extending the reach to targeted regional and thematic communities.
- Utilisation of partners’ digital channels and direct contacts - all partners supported the promotion by sharing event information through their own newsletters, websites, social media, and direct outreach to stakeholders and mailing lists.
- Development of a data space survey - a feedback survey was created and distributed via QR code at each Road Show event. It served to gather insights, impressions, and suggestions from attendees, supporting future improvements and scale-out strategy.
- Custom visuals were created for each Road Show, including event banners, digital flyers, roll-ups, and branded presentation templates to ensure a consistent and professional identity across all communication touchpoints. We ensured that all materials included EU funding emblem and the funding statement were possible.

5.4.2 Surveys

The UNDERPIN survey was designed to gather feedback from a diverse range of organizations, including research institutions, large industries, business support organizations, and small to medium-sized enterprises. The primary objective of the survey was to assess the level of interest, experience, and expectations regarding participation in the UNDERPIN Data Space, which aims to provide a trustworthy environment for data sharing.

The survey was conducted over a period spanning from December 2024 to November 2025. Respondents accessed the survey digitally, through a web-based tool, which is commonly used for such purposes and allows for easy distribution via link and QR code (Figure 21). The full questionnaire can be found in ANNEX XV.

At the start, the survey asked what kind of organization each person represented and whether they were open to sharing data in a secure environment like UNDERPIN. This helped the team see how ready different types of organizations are for this kind of collaboration. The answers showed a good mix of research groups, big companies, business support organizations, and small businesses. This variety is important because it means the data space could serve a wide range of needs.

The next part of the survey focused on experience. It asked if people had used digital platforms for sharing data before, like Data Spaces or Marketplaces, and what could be improved about those experiences. People pointed out that things like business models, rules for how the space

Figure 21 QR code for the survey

is run, and making sure different systems can work together (interoperability) are all areas that need attention. They also mentioned that having clear and consistent ways to describe and format data would help a lot.

Another set of questions asked what benefits organizations hoped to get from joining UNDERPIN. The survey let people choose what mattered most to them - like saving money, working more efficiently, being part of an innovative community, or finding new ways to do business. The responses showed that organizations are looking for a mix of practical and strategic benefits, and that these can be different depending on their goals.

The survey also wanted to know what roles people were interested in (like being a data provider or consumer) and how often they'd want to exchange data. The answers here were quite varied; some wanted to share data only when needed, while others were open to more regular or even real-time exchanges. This shows that any successful data space needs to be flexible and able to support different ways of working.

When it came to payment and concerns, the survey left room for people to explain their thoughts. Some said payment should be decided case by case, some thought it should be free, and others weren't responsible for financial decisions.

The main worries people had, were about data privacy, making sure different systems could work together, and having clear rules and governance. These are big issues that need to be addressed to build trust and make the data space work for everyone.

Finally, the survey asked what kinds of data people would be willing to share. Many said they'd share test data or data under certain conditions, but there were also limits - often because of privacy, competition, or legal reasons.

In summary, the UNDERPIN survey helped reveal what organizations really care about, what they need, and what might stop them from joining a shared data space. The feedback makes it clear that trust, clear rules, and the ability to work with different systems are all essential. There's a lot of interest in the idea, but success will depend on listening to these concerns and building a space that's flexible, secure, and truly useful for everyone involved.

5.5 Ambassador programme

The UNDERPIN Ambassador Programme was established to extend the visibility, impact, and sustainability of project results beyond the project's lifetime. The programme empowers selected consortium members and stakeholders to act as Ambassadors, representing UNDERPIN within the wider European data ecosystem and promoting the adoption of its principles and tools. It aims to establish a structured network of enthusiastic individuals and professionals who will actively support and promote the UNDERPIN Data Space across Europe. These ambassadors will act as multipliers, engaging with local, regional, and sector-specific communities to raise awareness, encourage adoption, and contribute to the long-term sustainability of the project.

5.5.1 Objectives and Rationale

The programme was conceived to extend UNDERPIN’s influence beyond the project consortium by empowering selected representatives – Ambassadors - to act as trusted advocates and multipliers of the project’s results. Within the Manufacturing Data Space, Ambassadors serve as bridges between research, industry, and policy communities, supporting the practical uptake of the project’s methodologies, tools, and frameworks.

The programme is designed to:

- Foster visibility and recognition of the UNDERPIN Data Space in industrial ecosystems.
- Enable stakeholder engagement through trusted local actors within the Manufacturing Data Space ecosystem.
- Promote awareness and adoption of trusted and interoperable data-sharing frameworks across manufacturing value chains.
- Support dissemination and scale-out efforts beyond traditional communication channels.
- Bridge the gap between the project consortium and real-world application environments.
- Support the replication and scaling of UNDERPIN solutions in other sectors and European regions.

This initiative will complement broader WP6 objectives and contribute to the project's outreach, impact, and community-building goals (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Visual structure of UNDERPIN Ambassador Programme

5.5.2 Methodology

Ambassadors are selected from among consortium partners and associated stakeholders based on their expertise, network reach, and active involvement in relevant use cases. Selection prioritises individuals or organizations with strong ties to manufacturing, data management, and standardisation communities. The implementation of the Ambassador Programme will follow a phased and flexible approach, ensuring scalability and inclusiveness across countries and sectors:

1. Identification and Selection of Ambassadors

Potential ambassadors will be identified through stakeholder mapping, partner recommendations, and open calls. Priority will be given to individuals with strong networks, communication skills, and a background in digital innovation, manufacturing, or data-driven transformation.

2. Onboarding and Support

Selected ambassadors will receive a comprehensive starter toolkit including branded materials, presentation templates, FAQs, and guidance documents. A central coordination point (partner contact) will facilitate ongoing support and knowledge exchange among ambassadors.

3. Role and Activities

Ambassadors will be invited to:

- Represent UNDERPIN at local and sectoral events.
- Share project news and opportunities within their networks.
- Collect feedback from stakeholders and report back to the consortium.
- Act as early advocates for UNDERPIN services and use cases.

4. Incentives and Recognition

While the programme is voluntary, incentives may include:

- Public recognition (project website, social media, newsletters).
- Participation in ambassador-only events or workshops.
- Certification of participation and potential inclusion in dissemination deliverables.

5. Monitoring and Evolution

Progress will be monitored based on engagement metrics (e.g., events attended, content shared), and the programme will be continuously refined based on ambassador feedback and project needs.

5.5.3 Expected Impact

The Ambassador Programme is expected to generate measurable impact across multiple dimensions of the UNDERPIN project:

- **Increased Visibility and Awareness:** Through ambassadors' outreach within their local, professional, and sectoral communities, the UNDERPIN Data Space will gain broader visibility, especially among hard-to-reach stakeholder groups and SMEs.
- **Stakeholder Engagement and Feedback Loop:** By acting as a bridge between the project and external audiences, ambassadors will help collect valuable insights and feedback, fostering a user-centric development and adoption process.
- **Support for Community Building:** Ambassadors will contribute to the formation of an engaged community around the UNDERPIN ecosystem, strengthening relationships with key actors across the manufacturing value chain.
- **Amplification of Dissemination Activities:** The programme will complement existing WP6 communication efforts by offering a decentralized, human-centric dissemination model, capable of adapting to different cultural and industrial contexts.
- **Long-term Sustainability:** The establishment of a trusted network of ambassadors will ensure that the project's outcomes, tools, and values are promoted beyond its formal end, increasing the likelihood of post-project uptake and continuity.

5.6 Collaborations and Cooperations

Over the course of the project, UNDERPIN established several collaborations and cooperations with external organisations and initiatives to amplify its reach, enhance its technical relevance, and foster community building. These interactions were important to aligning the project with broader European efforts around Data Spaces and digital manufacturing transformation.

The following table summarises key cooperation activities:

ORGANISATION	Activities and Contributions
DATASPACE 4.0	Participation in the Final event, exchange of ideas on manufacturing innovation assets from various perspectives.
SM4RTENANCE	Co-organisation of four joint webinars – the "Deep Dive" series – focusing on topics such as predictive maintenance, semantic interoperability, business models, and the Digital Product Passport. These are detailed in Chapter 5.2.
ADMA TranS4Mers	Participation at the Final event. Shared knowledge and strategic discussions on the uptake of digital transformation practices in manufacturing SMEs. Cross-promotional efforts were explored.

ORGANISATION	Activities and Contributions
IDSA (International Data Spaces Association)	Collaboration on shaping and communicating Data Space principles. UNDERPIN was included in IDSA’s ecosystem calls and technical discussions.
EIT Manufacturing, FLEX4RES, University of Patras	Joint organisation of the "TORPEDOES – Data Spaces Datathon" to promote practical experimentation and cross-project knowledge sharing.
Platform INDUSTRIE 4.0	Participation in their “Research Insights” webinar series, and joint support for the Vienna Road Show.
soviety	Engagement in interoperability, onboarding, and governance dialogues, aligning technical architectures and reusability of existing frameworks.
PHME24	Presentation & discussion of predictive maintenance for wind farms
DSSC (Data Space Support Centre)	Collaboration on organising a joint event and supporting the community building activities.

5.7 Standardisation and Certification

The UNDERPIN project has made measurable progress in aligning its research outputs with European and international standardization initiatives, particularly regarding semantic interoperability, data governance, and trusted data transactions. The Cyprus Organization for Standardization (CYS) has been engaged in facilitating and exploring these efforts toward potential committee participation and formal standard contributions.

UNDERPIN partners and CYS (represented by ICT Standards Officer Joseph Karis) established the scope and pathways for integrating UNDERPIN results into formal standardization activities. Discussions focused on:

- Establishing UNDERPIN liaison through CYS with CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 and ETSI TC DATA.
- Mapping UNDERPIN’s semantic interoperability components to Trusted Data Transactions (EN/TS CEN-CLC JTC 25), Data Catalogue Implementation Framework (ETSI Deliverable 4), and NGSI-LD Core API/Models (ETSI TC DATA).
- Evaluating committee membership options and defining the resources required for project-level participation in standardization.

CYS’s engagement ensures that national representation provides a formal conduit for UNDERPIN’s technical contributions to European data-related standards.

5.7.1 Standardization Bodies and Frameworks Engaged

5.7.1.1 CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 (Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge)

JTC 25 oversees standardization of Data Space architectures and governance frameworks. According to its May 2025 Plenary (document CEN-CLC-JTC 25_N131):

- Key Deliverables (2025–2026):
 - Trusted Data Transactions (Parts 1–3),
 - Quality Framework for Internal Data Governance,
 - Data Catalogue Implementation Framework,
 - Maturity Model for Common European Data Spaces.

- Collaboration Agreement:

A “Mode 4” liaison was established between ETSI TC DATA and CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 to synchronize efforts on the Trusted European Data Framework covering interoperability, trust, quality, and catalogue implementation deliverables.

Given UNDERPIN’s work on semantic layers and trusted data flows, CYS and project participants identified Trusted Data Transactions (Part 1-3) as directly relevant for potential contribution.

5.7.1.2 ETSI TC DATA (European Telecommunications Standards Institute)

ETSI TC DATA, formally approved in early 2025, functions as a central committee for distributed data infrastructures and semantics.

- Relevant Work Items (WIs) include:
 - NGSI-LD Core API and Information Model,
 - SAREF and NGSI-LD integration for data interoperability,
 - Guidelines for Data Catalogue Framework (Deliverable 4) addressing common catalogue specifications under the Data Act,
 - Trusted Data Framework Guidelines for Semantic Interoperability,
 - Quality Metrics for Data Trustworthiness.

UNDERPIN’s architecture around Vocabulary Hubs and semantic metadata can support these ETSI domains, particularly under NGSI-LD API conformance and semantic extensions.

5.7.2 UNDERPIN’s outputs related to Standards

Insofar, the UNDERPIN project has identified several technical and pre-normative outputs relevant to standardization processes:

- Advancing Semantic Interoperability:

UNDERPIN extends beyond syntactic standards (IDS, GAIA-X) by introducing dynamic semantic mapping - linking meaning to data columns and datasets for cross-domain data understanding.

- Pre-Normative Semantic Layer:

Implementation of a Semantic Layer using tools like PoolParty and GraphDB acts as a proof-of-concept standard for embedding semantic services within Data Spaces.

- Dynamic Semantic Mapping Standards:

Through ontology-based data access (OBDA), R2RML, and CSVW frameworks, UNDERPIN provides a scalable approach to semantic harmonization, potentially influencing upcoming ETSI and JTC 25 specifications on metadata governance.

- Vocabulary Hub:

The enhanced Vocabulary Hub supplies a reusable component for the Data Catalogue Implementation Framework (CEN/CLC JTC 25 and ETSI D4) and related trust mechanisms.

5.7.3 CYS Involvement and Future Actions

- Facilitated the mapping of UNDERPIN's outputs to existing European standardization workstreams.
- Opened communication between UNDERPIN and JTC 25/ETSI coordinators for potential comment submission and technical input.

Next steps agreed involve:

1. Submission of recommendations or commentary to relevant JTC 25 deliverables (Trusted Data Transactions, Internal Data Governance Quality).
2. Exploration of project liaison application through CYS to ETSI.
3. Integration of UNDERPIN's semantic framework results into upcoming ETSI publications on NGS-LD testing and data catalogue interoperability.

5.7.4 Contributions towards SPDX 3.0 Specification

Another activity of the UNDERPIN consortium towards standardisation are the contributions made towards the SPDX ontology and data model through Github issues, discussions and participation in Working Group meetings.

The System Package Data Exchange (SPDX) is an open standard for communicating SBOM information, including provenance, license, security, and other related information. SPDX version 2.2.1 was standardized as ISO/IEC 5962:2021. The SPDX 3.0 specification is under active development and significantly expands the scope of the standard, encompassing AI models, datasets and more.

In UNDERPIN the SPDX specification is used in the data model for the project's software Digital Product Passports. UNDERPIN consortium members have made suggestions for improvements of SPDX in relation to:

- Modelling of Identifiers, including adding extra details about IdentifierTypes
- Reusing prior modelling efforts, such as
 - QUDT for unit definitions (as in UNDERPIN's data model)

- Ontotext's earlier work on Semantization of Machine Learning and Data Science presented at Big Data Value Association Activity Group 45 (BDVA AG 45), Sep 2021
 - SHACL Simplification and Rationalization, including modularization of property shapes, simplifying shape checks and more
 - Ontology descriptions
 - Namespaces versioning and stability

The expanded scope of SPDX 3.0 offers ample opportunity for further contributions towards standardization efforts, as well as further applications in relation to Digital Product Passports for software, datasets, AI models and more.

5.7.5 Summary

By October 2025, UNDERPIN has transitioned from exploratory alignment to direct mapping of its semantic interoperability outputs to European standardization processes. Through its collaboration with CYS, it is positioned to contribute concretely to the Trusted Data Framework and Data Catalogue standards under CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 and ETSI TC DATA. The project's Vocabulary Hub and Semantic Layer implementations serve as tangible pre-standardization assets bridging research outputs with European interoperability standards and the evolving *Common European Data Space* framework.

6 Exploitation and Continuation

The exploitation of the project’s results is a key objective of the UNDERPIN consortium, is targeted to ensure scientific progress beyond the state-of-the art, and support economic sustainability of the results after the project’s completion. The exploitation plan for UNDERPIN outlines how project results will be used, by whom, and through which channels, to maximize long-term impact across the European industrial data ecosystem. It aligns with the European Data Strategy, the Data Governance Act, and the forthcoming Data Act, supporting secure, interoperable, and sovereign data exchange across manufacturing, energy, and other asset-intensive sectors.

6.1 Market Context

The global Data Space and data marketplace market is rapidly growing, projected to exceed USD 4 billion by 2030 with a CAGR of 20-25%, driven by enterprise investments in data monetization, AI, and federated analytics. At the same time, European initiatives such as Gaia-X, Catena-X, and IDSA provide technical, governance, and trust frameworks that facilitate secure cross-organizational collaboration.

UNDERPIN is strategically positioned as a Pan-European industrial Data Space, combining federated architecture, sovereign access control, and data monetization mechanisms. It enables trusted data exchange, dynamic asset management, and interoperable ecosystem formation, reinforcing Europe’s digital competitiveness

6.2 Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Key Exploitable Results refer to the concrete or abstract outcomes of an action, such as data, knowledge, and information, regardless of their form or nature. These results are identified as high-priority elements for exploitation activities. The UNDERPIN consortium has identified a set of KERs, each of which contributes strategically to the development and enhancement of the Data Space value chain (Table 8).

Table 8 UNDERPIN Key Exploitable Results

KER	Description	Beneficiaries	Exploitation Pathway
FEDERATED DATA SPACE ARCHITECTURE	Modular, cloud-based, federated infrastructure enabling secure, interoperable, and sovereign data exchange	Data providers, data consumers, Data Space operators, service providers	Adoption as reference architecture, integration in partner platforms, foundation for new EU projects
TECHNICAL TOOLKITS AND CONNECTORS	Modular tools for secure data access, storage, and transfer, including EDC connectors, APIs,	SMEs, technology providers, industrial operators	Commercial integration, open-access pilots, consultancy services

KER	Description	Beneficiaries	Exploitation Pathway
	CaaS deployment, time-series databases		
GOVERNANCE, COMPLIANCE, AND SECURITY FRAMEWORKS	Legal, trust, and compliance mechanisms including smart contracts, encryption, RBAC/ABAC, and EU Data Space compliance	Regulatory bodies, standardization organizations, data providers/consumer, service providers	Adoption as best-practice template, contribution to EU policy/standards, consulting/certification services
KNOWLEDGE ASSETS	Deliverables, white papers, technical reports, datasets, and open-access publications capturing project insights and standards	Academia, research organizations, policy/standardization bodies, industrial stakeholders	Open-access publications, training workshops, webinars,

6.3 Exploitation Objectives

The UNDERPIN consortium established a clear exploitation strategy, defined by specific objectives from the beginning of the project, to guide post-project sustainability efforts. These objectives are summarized as follows:

1. **Enable Trusted Data Sharing:** Support the creation of interoperable and secure industrial Data Spaces aligned with the European Data Strategy.
2. **Support Dynamic and Reusable Assets:** Deliver modular and standards-based components (technical and governance) for replication in other sectors.
3. **Promote Adoption:** Position UNDERPIN as a reference implementation for Data Space interoperability within and beyond the consortium.
4. **Ensure Long-Term Value Creation:** Facilitate commercial and operational uptake by SMEs, manufacturers, and service providers.
5. **Foster Collaboration:** Strengthen cooperation with European initiatives such as Gaia-X, IDSA, and the Data Space Support Centre (DSSC).

The exploitation outcomes of the UNDERPIN project are based on three main inputs:

1. **Market Context:** A thorough understanding of the evolving market landscape helps identify and evaluate exploitation opportunities. By situating UNDERPIN within the

broader commercial and research ecosystem, the project gains insight into competitive advantages and differentiators, supporting strong market positioning.

2. **Project Capabilities and Constraints:** Internal capabilities and constraints define what can realistically be achieved, highlighting the unique value and innovation embedded in UNDERPIN. This analysis also accounts for limitations arising from licensing decisions and the capacity of consortium partners to engage in post-project commercial or collaborative activities.
3. **Individual Partners' Interests and Opportunities:** Each partner's strategy balances near-term goals with the overarching long-term vision of the project. Aligning individual objectives with the consortium's collective strategy ensures maximum value creation and impact. The specific interests and opportunities of partners are closely linked to their organizational nature, whether private for-profit companies or R&D non-profit entities.

Figure 23 below, describes the exploitation pathway of UNDERPIN, highlighting the key opportunities that inform the exploitation strategy, including the strategic partnerships, and competitive advantage.

Figure 23 UNDERPIN opportunities for exploitation

6.4 Beneficiaries and Target Stakeholders

Section 3 of Deliverable *D5.1 Existing Business Models Assessment*, presents a comprehensive stakeholder analysis within the European data ecosystem. Building on this, the exploitation activities of UNDERPIN aim to create value for a diverse set of actors across the European data economy, focusing on the following sectors:

- a) Energy,
- b) Oil and gas, and
- c) Manufacturing.

The main stakeholder categories include:

- SMEs and Technology Providers: Will leverage the developed connectors, APIs, and frameworks to create new data-driven products and services.
- Manufacturers and Energy Operators: Can enhance operational efficiency and resilience through trusted and interoperable data-sharing models.
- Data Providers and Consumers: Benefit from a secure, compliant, and standardised environment for industrial data exchange.
- Policy and Standardisation Bodies: Gain access to evidence-based insights supporting future regulatory and standardisation developments.
- Research and Academia: Utilize the openly available tools and knowledge assets to advance further research, innovation, and educational activities.

6.5 Commercialisation Strategy

As outlined in Section 5 of Deliverable *D5.3 Business, Engagement and Commercialisation Plan*, the commercialisation strategy for UNDERPIN is designed to maximize the full impact of the project developments and prepare the transition towards market uptake, in order to ensure the exploitation beyond the project itself. It builds upon the project's core principles of data sovereignty, interoperability, and trust, and is aligned with the frameworks and tools established by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA).²

6.6 Exploitation Channels and Tools

To ensure visibility and uptake, the consortium applied a multi-channel exploitation approach throughout the project. This included the organisation of dedicated events and participation in

² Verbrugge, S., Herregodts, A.-L., Kraemer, P., Heindl, A., Schlüter-Langdon, C., Gelhaar, J., Schäfer, M., de Roode, M., & Verstraete, M. (2024). *Data Spaces Business Models (Version 1.0)* [Position paper]. International Data Spaces Association. Source: https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Position-Paper-Data-Spaces-Business-Models.pdf (internationaldataspaces.org)

major industrial and research conferences, workshops, and forums, where project outcomes, use case demonstrations, and technical solutions were presented to target audiences. These included:

- Roadshows and Industrial Events: Demonstration of UNDERPIN results and use cases and engagement with potential adopters and policymakers (as described in the chapters *5.1 Participation at Events* and *5.3 Road Show Events* of this document).
- Public Dissemination: Publication of results via Zenodo, project website, and open-access repositories (as described in the chapters *4.7 Zenodo* and *4.8 Publications*, of this document).
- Digital Outreach: Active communication through newsletters, social media channels, and specialized forums to target domain communities (as described in the chapters *4.3 Social Media*, *4.5 Press Releases and Media Mentions* and *4.6 Newsletters* of this document).

7 Conclusion

The communication and dissemination activities carried out under WP6 successfully supported the visibility, uptake, and impact of the UNDERPIN project. Through consistent efforts across digital and physical channels, the consortium has built awareness around the concept of industrial Data Spaces and engaged key stakeholders across Europe.

The UNDERPIN project's social media strategy aligned with current best practices for EU digital innovation projects. By focusing on platforms that support professional communication, content dissemination, and community building, the project ensured targeted outreach and maximised visibility among relevant stakeholders. The prioritisation of LinkedIn and YouTube allowed the team to deliver meaningful, industry-relevant content to the right audiences, while avoiding ineffective or outdated channels. This strategic focus contributed to the project's strong digital footprint and supported the overall goal of promoting the UNDERPIN Data Space across EU's manufacturing and innovation landscape.

The project achieved nearly all planned KPIs and exceeded several, particularly in terms of publications, event participation, and cross-project collaborations. Lessons learned during implementation were met with flexible responses that maintained momentum and relevance.

Overall, best practices identified through this project include:

- Focus communication efforts on platforms that align with your audience (e.g., LinkedIn for industry-focused stakeholders).
- Invest in clear, consistent project branding from the outset.
- Integrate educational tools like explainer videos to demystify complex technical topics.
- Prioritise strategic collaborations to extend the project's reach and relevance.
- Maintain flexibility in the communication plan to adapt to real-world conditions and emerging opportunities.

UNDERPIN's experience shows that combining a solid strategy with adaptable, audience-driven outreach enables meaningful impact even in technically complex domains.

However, one important conclusion emerged: awareness and understanding of Data Spaces remain limited, particularly among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Despite increasing attention at the EU level, onboarding SMEs into Data Spaces continues to be a challenge. Many companies still perceive Data Spaces as complex, with unclear value propositions and a lack of easy-to-use onboarding tools.

Moreover, it is crucial to foster cooperation rather than competition among Data Space initiatives. Fragmentation, duplication of efforts, and limited collaboration can hinder interoperability, delay uptake, and erode trust. Stronger cross-project alignment could accelerate adoption and make Data Spaces more accessible, scalable, and impactful across the EU.

As UNDERPIN transitions from implementation to exploitation, the communication and dissemination foundations laid by WP6 will continue to play a critical role. The networks, materials, and community engagement mechanisms established through this work package form a valuable legacy to support the future growth of the European manufacturing Data Space ecosystem.

Annexes

ANNEX I

Abstract of visuals used to communicate the project, events and results, on digital channels

ANNEX II

List of post published on digital channels of the project

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
1	22.12.23	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpinproject-manufacturing-underpindataspace-activity-7143912034508722176-xELT?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
2	22.12.23	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0mKRggscBLkAZ6hNTrKPCMoOQs9QL7Wn6ZaHy2DkDKJJfozap3vHvXyMAMWsisoPS2l
3	22.12.23	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1738169791104401416?s=20
4	9.1.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7150491162666078208
5	9.1.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02WQi8ca4wEHE9hAMPxgiKtkqxbLoSPA3bmXviwSkVY47bCuZNCVBABREA2SmY7Tvl
6	9.1.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1744728406909141503?s=20
7	18.1.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7153680325284356096
8	18.1.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid09sZX47kT1bGawpYmdStPPyfWzt2S7LgQGHjxBbAWrpGc89LYKHuiCCkjtUJcAayNl
9	18.1.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1747917129754571040?s=20
10	19.1.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/2024/01/19/marking-the-launch-of-the-underpin-project/
11	1.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158756675716354048
12	1.2.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid01A3AVcS7jdawnzb4YHNu7wAQP7hMhmMWzzkbhb3m8pQpcJbZ9sT2ofgQcMJ7o6Y4l
13	1.2.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1752996109608255952?s=20
14	14.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7163426694207336448
15	14.2.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid022uVrsVMnqK2SLuGgauTvseitiaheTnKwyfFaWfUNwLTKV32tzAxAXWvGpkkRUVYl
16	14.2.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1757670258402537497?s=20
17	14.2.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/2024/02/13/underpin-updates-technical-requirements-workshop-vienna/
18	26.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7167831171962134529
19	26.2.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0ZWixd5DwTZQeS4vMcCTivPgygrxekAVg2hge257uma5VbgeTstzWtKB8UgYnzSxl
20	26.2.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1762078162299551784?s=20
21	4.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7170417726123937792
22	4.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0GEPoEzGQt9o9gH8ZBUyx73Y8mUFTZS5HBMrJn3eF7Th86WDDxLoeFBjU5oDMvPTxl
23	4.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1764561419478151301?s=20
24	7.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171505080859250689
25	7.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02om1MTEec56ESftULyeMTXHjrMZ6gG6VDAeJmrrM9QYzLgsZTo8phJ7XmRHdFHHvPl
26	7.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1765657136351367221?s=20
27	8.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171837123564703744
28	8.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0Z4d68dqaSaVmed7A8mH7734m4KT513RQKdgpTmJUdievX9fkhfFXpJK4qY1HLFl
29	8.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1766004676175020149?s=20
30	11.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7172939356502978560

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
31	11.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid027v7yJnTVmhCrq929dD2wHdmmtuMndjE1qydqZ26WuBiQmbtgzyuBLhnuApT8WmX3l
32	11.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1767086806422495595?s=20
33	14.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7174011438561169408
34	14.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0qzRhLCword92WuUH8Me593CE4aVpoBWT7ELR92DC62mKRfbk2CU6RFmjXE513Ymal
35	14.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1768255759408898300?s=20
36	18.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7175468500419756032
37	18.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid031KtXop2FHCMwH1RTLtgZUppBJHdAugee7XW8ytrQfCoBA4a3H9sH6kNBxP8BPGDZl
38	18.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1769636859498693001?s=20
39	18.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/international-data-spaces-association_the-data-spaces-radar-march-2024-4-activity-7176595671947354113-fuO-?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
40	18.3.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-in-the-new-data-spaces-radar-report/
41	19.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7175823352614318081
42	19.3.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0ypCEtHsPERsx8NrH9wXhR5gzkkWnkL7hDuiym9rGcPZw5ZjFfVDULA7eajtRypefl
43	19.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1770012336436469784?s=20
44	21.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7176548136658608129
45	21.3.24	FB	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02xa87ULV51SuRfYqZDkjccY2heErveYxDLPbKRNHYap7ZyNLPWmkdQMt7HrRuSvl
46	21.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1770895905819890051?s=20
47	22.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7176866194933637121
48	25.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7178005237738205184
49	25.3.24	FB	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0kipTcgM4ALFYJ8EHTrHqB3wYU4oHozNmA7EQrvu1rGA81nr64x3t345sWSU9zaAl
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51	25.3.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zWYLFg5DDR8
52	28.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7179099926654533634
53	28.3.24	FB	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0QaY1i2hDaGKX1A5raNDe6KwJESim1oDBkA4nZQ7GS97Zjs23T25Hs8k7rAxH3CA7l
54	28.3.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1773267784652230780?s=20
55	2.4.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-project-presented-at-data-space-symposium-2024/
56	3.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181198782502486016
57	3.4.24	FB	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0YGLAKKXFBPLAYGqosJ2rdrvuV1ZvS6eQCDLSwq8Mhmkj7FwMXaazQQFkUV1guAHI
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61	5.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1776165379410149395
62	6.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mbuchhorn_idsa-new-publications-activity-7176356936987107328-68vS/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
63	8.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kQDpN57erU0&t=4s
64	8.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183010725487919105
65	8.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02SgCMrkmVYc4dyVEHCciPX whaoJPAYbsP1GMDPCWYDaqPNq7t1hxeWHnqqgSjFjXdl
66	8.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1777255812664107355
67	8.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VmlNbmj4-ew
68	9.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F_CVdIAAlpl&t=2s
69	9.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_oV878WN5LU
70	9.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jjKEXRS24XQ
71	9.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R9w7iMtPE7M
72	9.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/faelbl_9-check-in-der-gaia-x-hub-austria-domain-activity-7184315020044820480-ORd3?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
73	11.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7184143159021428736
74	11.4.24	Facebook	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02uaAbTUxBisTgCNGdcLKWW A4zWeszpWBhV8V86z8hWzenFXrXhCf9d6CF9HyZHWpl
75	11.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1778337691404239065
76	11.4.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QiC5CNtkbCM
77	15.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7185592724165640193
78	15.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0AR58UnxzmFnCFa1VSKHj9H JgYxvjinAYLciRNH5kiTWNCF2NX3XG5BXbgx7aaRsKl
79	15.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1779781709091017141
80	17.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/olga-galanets-a1aa8681_agriculture-culturalheritage-energy-activity-7188944686999289859-9gH9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
81	18.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7186672320667672576
82	18.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid031m96AtQV7Scz4iqbqvZ34s d1pUvaGPU9UWHZv2JPJBDmJQoiSvshJNwJSxmXKgXql
83	18.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1780868870997512316
84	18.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/strategis-maritime-center-of-excellence_decarbonization-digitalization-sustainability-activity-7175565684775526400-rTrz?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
85	22.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188121877859483651
86	22.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid021Zg4Sq4K4qqcH99K8qi81T HH94aMqMQ9asJ7GRx4AK67aMYRZS4ApJvznMu3yBM1l
87	22.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1782318429892129158
88	25.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7189209042311929858
89	25.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0n3yv1FSVFLdtkdMF3BX1Kw BMQGGGwUY3Syidgkx6P6nGq9bwKdgge542tn5BFQvtl
90	25.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1783412379939926452

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
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92	29.4.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02yGyxsN9yfab6itgVrn9xHi2sh88W5LMuGCyAgGg4FxxM986mmvNV7Q1DBdmcUyisl
93	29.4.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1784859414790324354
94	30.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7191014126020673536
95	2.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7191707995318239233
96	2.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02MghDy1SBJTJ2GHFFzk993MPKzSA8wtJGkciCrBuxX2oiUkExWRDrGvBmrZ7y9VSLl
97	2.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1785942309000949803
98	3.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7192090876297322497
99	3.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0sQ2mXZh4F7Sr3i2LBSNLxqi vonK94XmkiYPchwZWeehk9vodStfwKy75dpJYfJmI
100	3.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1786327485795147930
101	6.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7193157623980974080
102	6.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0agghoL9Av3jowoNhK5KyxTdJ YgmaYmJL9foRui7Qg69dstT7tTPVvq5zark4Lx3Fl
103	6.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1787391856214450268
104	9.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7194244776483815425
105	9.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0X8w9TyVvYXyNqx4UjH5RiN VH5v8DMANcj5Au6GoBTMofwiArdSRLHfcqncCN4GeAl
106	9.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1788479025255719177
107	14.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7196067645106884610
108	14.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0652v7PBb2ZAXvRaqV3kQBD WX2NXyqFqUsoi8YJEN82N46kENJrZx3sTYEKA7trtJl
109	15.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7196506416885469184
110	15.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid07UHYvAhujcUFC1QbC4XxZ2 GAC3xgJZKVTelW81aUdA5MTfZcCUWPw2SohUp1ht8zl
109	15.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1790741815894704270
110	17.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7197211184243044353
111	17.5.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02prca7P8GwFjN6Bhz36KAc MCXkRj2Tte4XEyh7BQKxxtsnfRdXP1zD9Cg1uXsfo7Gf
112	17.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1791447069372096536
113	17.5.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/the-first-general-assembly-of-the-underpin-project/
114	28.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201124757453361152
115	28.5.24	FB	https://fb.watch/stn8JTNxWo/
116	28.5.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1795361105344106513
117	3.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203352077459193856
118	3.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203369873043816448
119	3.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0Mwg8b7Eo2Cnb5QievDNeH ZGMiwMF5n74mtNsCKJQV6JPNjxfP1oFAjqNbgTZJRdvl
120	3.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1797606387222245610
121	4.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203712719634477056
122	5.6.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/publication-adapting-ontology-based-data-access-for-data-spaces/

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
123	6.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204429351864459264
124	6.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02s3jp3e2wxOe27sk62SgaMBQAEJ5zQqcJFff1NSMh2NM5S1pQstBXcVkv4zVKrGjI
125	6.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1798627134644031614
126	7.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204753957938728960
127	7.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0HBpCYHXzWyzEhpT3udqYW3b29ic5cBa2obZTBTPsbLLdGyMaJwemmd4ajn2FC52bl
128	7.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1798988263237304740
129	10.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7205826530537619456
130	10.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02g8RsANKtLcBJDq3e2UA6C2tpiY4QdVUqzpvzuoMw4ERfxar4zMBqdVpTTPpP8v7HI
131	10.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1800055299849495019
132	12.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206581109470425089
133	12.6.24	FB	https://fb.watch/t6baz_p5jO/
134	12.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1800802467539456335
135	12.6.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/dataspace-4-0-final-event-in-brussels/
136	13.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206973617937539073
137	13.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid031G1zNzuKSSfXuCbPjhm7YamN12qh1kLBNSo5Ngt5kGUbPKxkx17ifPtP3cfCNpJSl
138	13.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1801167372046446632
139	17.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7208377866974113792
140	17.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0v2xgZpOteNmrrBB5T3Xkm8gMkwWptmaFuKi3PFb8XnnjTGGeHiugfoZ55uGHWUpBl
141	17.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1802618181707542695
142	20.6.24	FB	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7209502794704179200
143	20.6.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02jTXUSyXYj2G6r9qi1PiiQiaXmux3VuRZW3DSiKztbRoCS53J4FrSnBYzJrJAM8Sl
144	20.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1803707358725460118
145	24.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7210914614438486016
146	24.6.24	FB	https://fb.watch/t6b3zHzRIZ/
147	24.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1805153135213813773
148	27.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7212009272769990657
149	27.6.24	FB	https://fb.watch/t6b285_e6N/
150	27.6.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1806242312013390209
151	1.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7213451294861135873
152	1.7.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02TYoxZsQpmYk7w9XFvm5KvizUycUPVaPC814CoTobGmnCQK9PGdYfx6F6QeZEQH73I
153	1.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1807685571923394764
154	2.7.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/data-spaces-guide-1/

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
155	3.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7214181053324816384
156	3.7.24	FB	https://fb.watch/t6a_EzmNH2/
157	3.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1808417651565195396
158	4.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7214538461549051905
159	4.7.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid033U1dbHp5eiwB7RZugDutq89MLzNXehyvkZQVigOrJEAPYZz8Hkr9woz8YxCFsuA3l
160	4.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1808772740343566369
161	4.7.24	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/introduction-data-spaces-underpinproject-0zkof/?trackingId=eMKkuTYdNR2mgzUhXWh%2B8w%3D%3D
162	8.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7215988039112683520
163	8.7.24	FB	https://fb.watch/toEvqv3OL/
164	8.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1810222291030069513
165	8.7.24	YouTube	https://youtu.be/-KL5KynbTKc?si=u662RYmiApOcZYqX
166	11.7.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid02z75Z7m8BczNMpjLfvYGvtjQX3aWjGRyXmAmxSzXiDEETpgnaEecn9fAdii4DXSRwl?_rdc=1&_rdr
167	11.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1811310206111948813
168	15.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7218524697259319296
169	15.7.24	FB	https://fb.watch/toEJrBaXlc/
170	15.7.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1812759004872863784
171	15.7.24	YouTube	https://youtu.be/3BNeC7NAUt0?si=Vt--KCes7GtWtjTt
172	22.7.24	YouTube	https://youtu.be/zpSK_AN7V5l?si=EwYlWd_qnZevNEDS
173	22.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpin-edu-key-components-of-data-spaces-activity-7221061424767217664-6yDy?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
174	22.7.24	FB	https://fb.watch/txXZJtRORb/
175	22.7.24	Twitter (X)	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1815297227192996201
176	29.7.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l8zNocMwWN4
177	29.7.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_implementation-challenges-of-data-spaces-activity-7223598209162477569-z_aG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
178	29.7.24	LinkedIn	https://fb.watch/tEy-dX5Wrg/
179	29.7.24	LinkedIn	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1817832684632371234
180	5.8.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7226134903006855168
181	5.8.24	FB	https://fb.watch/tOp4sCCBCz/
182	5.8.24	Twitter (X)	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1820369149987901536
183	5.8.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z7UsK06zOk
184	6.8.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/data-spaces-guide-2/
185	7.8.24	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7226859682198351872
186	8.8.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid035jdTtKh8xTs8ANCjN2rNEju5AboULM8BApSAa9v9rhEDuwEAWnrg1LxwFCGPELGt
187	8.8.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1821456314570268931
188	12.8.24	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K-m6Ppnw0BU

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
189	12.8.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7228671668565471232
190	12.8.24	FB	https://fb.watch/tVET0dM2_U/
191	12.8.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1822905864795324717
192	19.8.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_datamanagement-underpindataspace-dataspaces-activity-7231208285612199936-PjVb?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
193	19.8.24	FB	https://fb.watch/u32ih5plFZ/
194	19.8.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1825442577320935810
195	26.8.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_predictivemaintenance-manufacturing-smes-activity-7233745007977893889-YSJT?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
196	26.8.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=122157411668124969&set=a.122115172214124969
197	26.8.24	LinkedIn	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1827979301506945398
198	3.9.24	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7236644116892139521
199	3.9.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/predictive-maintenance-revolutionizing-equipment-care/
200	9.9.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1833052725736616316
201	9.9.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122159367848124969&set=a.122115172214124969
202	9.9.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7238818435093135360
203	17.9.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/predictive-maintenance-in-the-context-of-underpin/
204	17.9.24	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7241717569357787138
205	17.9.24	FB	https://web.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122160497606124969&set=a.122115172214124969
206	17.9.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1835951826832626037
207	1.10.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7247002265109057536
208	7.10.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-at-the-semantic-interoperability-workshop-and-ebdvf-2024/
209	11.10.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7250369592076759040
210	11.10.24	FB	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace/posts/pfbid0T9B8w1RTN5koEJvaknNvvvgMRj6MgiH4Hr6EhrHATJVYVPHMX3B9g1C726rjzAmGl
211	11.10.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1844649137050091922
212	18.11.24	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264240567046307840
213	18.11.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpins-second-general-assembly-in-vienna/
214	18.11.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1858516006659895433
215	21.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7265273719294492673
216	22.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7265663480580505600

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
217	22.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7265672627300487168
218	26.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7267174914430816256
219	26.11.24	FB	https://fb.watch/x_Rqx1sTVX/
220	26.11.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1861412463377367139
221	26.11.24	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1861412870593958378
222	26.11.24	Facebook	https://web.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=122170270898124969&set=a.122115172214124969
223	4.12.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-presented-at-adma-trans4mers-final-event-in-brussels/
224	4.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270063753713393664
225	5.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270341535638974466
226	18.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7275158075706068992
227	20.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7275766885651009536
228	23.12.24	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/the-1st-underpin-roadshow-held-in-athens/
229	23.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7276850269223591936
230	28.1.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7290030341350723584
231	5.2.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7292806111194238976
232	7.2.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293680494590803969
233	5.3.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7302946077060571137
234	10.3.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7304783248759386113
235	12.3.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7305496378741301248
236	1.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7312746596532731904
237	1.4.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/role-data-spaces-advancing-eus-clean-industrial-deal-xdckf/?trackingId=rDwGlrAHlWuqme4I7YlwMA%3D%3D
238	1.4.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/the-role-of-data-spaces-in-advancing-the-eus-clean-industrial-deal/
239	4.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7313802542872707072
240	10.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7316007137795629057
241	17.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7318543815928119296
242	23.4.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/join-us-for-the-sm4rt-underpin-deep-dives/
243	23.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7320687958037024768
244	23.4.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/join-us-sm4rt-underpin-deep-dives-underpinproject-zk1ef/?trackingId=mCSKGw6zqLLAjZ5QkEQtw%3D%3D
245	24.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7321065442310008833
246	24.4.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/join-us-at-the-underpin-road-show-in-maribor/

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
247	25.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7321412656735633408
248	25.4.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/join-us-underpin-road-show-maribor-underpinproject-hwmif/?trackingId=Tmk2AINX%2FP7ExvF9dA7RNQ%3D%3D
249	28.4.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7322484729117585408
250	6.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7325492873569714176
251	7.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7325791601652297728
252	9.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7326516393565163520
253	12.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7326528459013287937
254	12.5.2025	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1921822829961478484
255	12.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7327558159923875840
256	16.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7329088713395720192
257	21.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330868475051065345
258	21.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330903243205562368
259	22.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7331330309185081346
260	27.5.2025	X	https://x.com/UnderpinProject/status/1927445229201653972
261	28.5.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333371495793987585
262	28.5.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333430913273376771
263	28.5.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpins-3rd-general-assembly-and-the-road-show-in-maribor/
264	2.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335188295271788545
265	3.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335545861990498304
266	6.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7336662552426250240
267	10.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7338196504953638913
268	10.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7338101192251650048
269	10.6.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/paper-presentation-at-phm-2025-in-bruges/
270	20.6.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7341757058922217473
271	3.7.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-showcased-at-ai-connected-business-world-2025-in-athens/
272	3.7.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7346469169258770432
273	11.7.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/join-us-at-the-underpin-road-show-in-vienna/
274	24.7.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7354096825877905408
275	7.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7359125905262133248

No	Date	Media	Link to the post
276	11.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7360550567619739648
277	14.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7361713224540393472
278	18.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363087256804306944
279	21.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7364249990862430208
280	25.8.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7365616479242698752
281	1.9.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7368145647977353216
282	12.9.2025	Website	https://underpinproject.eu/news/underpin-road-show-vienna-bringing-data-spaces-closer-to-industry/
283	12.9.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7372262404040196097
284	15.9.2025	Newsletter Lin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7373226569957441536
285	16.9.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7373829448057491456
286	18.9.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7374325073995792384
287	26.9.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7377243766429995008
288	11.11.2025	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7394003041177370624
289	13.11.2025.	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7394692071267270656
290	18.11.2025.	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7396472351409983488

ANNEX III

List of Articles and PRs

No	Date	Type	Lang	Target	URL link to the publication
1	4.2.2024	Article	SLO	SMEs	https://www.finance.si/subvencije/tako-slovinci-z-evropskimi-partnerji-gradijo-podatkovne-prostore/a/9020748
2	12.2.2024	Article	SLO	SMEs	https://www.zelenaslovenija.si/zeleno-omrezje/vzpostavitev-vseevropskega-proizvodnega-podatkovnega-prostora/
3	13.2.2024	Article	SLO	SMEs	https://www.sbc.si/novice/2024/02/tiko-pro-kot-kljucni-partner-pri-evropskem-projektu-za-digitalizacijo-industrije
4	15.2.2024	Video	CRO/EN	SMEs	https://esma.tiko-pro.si/obrazec-poduzetnicki-video?utm_source=ESMA&utm_medium=ESMA&utm_campaign=novosti&fbclid=IwAR0dx0vCgLwBI87AAhy1ytHFxSTIFniqXzyobzkUeGir9WIporo1odRKEel_aem_AbT0ic88Zoj6uBbxVbfg5jUY46zHekeB6GJTJQfm2n4WqS31LHGRfErOFc4ZZmtuKsP29d4OmFZd7yAzmwaOWY76
5	13.3.2024	Article	EN	SC	https://internationaldataspace.org/adopt/dataspace-radar/
6	2.5.2025	PR	SLO	SMEs	https://www.sbc.si/novice/2025/05/underpin-road-show-odkrijte-prihodnost-podatkovnih-prostorov-v-proizvodni-industriji
7	10.5.2025	PR	SLO	SMEs	https://dih Slovenia.si/aktualno/dogodki/vabilo-na-mednarodni-dogodek-underpin-road-show-maribor
8	16.5.2024	PR	SLO	General Public	https://podjetnaslovenija.si/trendi/tiko-pro-v-66-milijonskem-projektu-za-digitalizacijo-industrije/
9	28.5.2025	Article	EN	SMEs	https://www.tiko-pro.eu/news/details/tiko-pro-leads-the-way-in-hosting-underpins-general-assembly-and-road-show-in-maribor
10	6.7.2025	Article	SLO	General Public	https://www.zelenaslovenija.si/zeleno-omrezje/eu-projekt-za-trajnostno-prihodnost-v-proizvodnji/

Table explanation: PR – press release, SC – scientific community, SLO – Slovenian, EN - English

ANNEX IV

Partner publications

No	Date	Type of post	Link to the post
1	12.4.24	General News	https://www.space.gr/en/UNDERPIN
2	1.3.24	General News	https://innov-acts.com/projects/
3	1.3.24	General News	https://www.w-melon.com/en/portfolio
4	18.2.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.hr/uspjesne-price/pojedinosti/underpin-digital-europe-konzorcijski-projekt
5	16.3.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.si/novica/tiko-pro-kljucni-partner-mednarodnega-projekta-underpin
6	1.2.24	General News	https://www.imsi.athenarc.gr/el/projects/project/90
7	3.6.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.hr/detalji/generalnom-skupstinom-obiljezeno-prvih-6-mjeseci-projekta-underpin
8	18.2.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.eu/success-stories/details/underpin-digital-europe-consortium-project
9	3.6.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.si/novica/projekt-underpin-obelezujemo-sest-mesecev-izvajanja-projekta-s-prvo-generalno-skupscino-konzorcija
10	3.6.24	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.eu/news/details/underpin-project-marking-the-six-months-with-the-first-general-assembly
11	24.1.24	General News	https://semantic-web.com/research/projects/
12	9.2.24	General News	https://www.ontotext.com/company/news/ontotext-joins-the-underpin-project/
13	9.2.24	General News	https://www.ontotext.com/knowledgehub/current/underpin/
14	10.2.25	General News	https://graphwise.ai/news/graphwise-participated-with-3-keynotes-in-aioti-workshop-on-semantic-interoperability-for-digital-twins/
15	11.3.25	Event	https://icsa.hua.gr/news.html
16	9.5.2025	Event	https://dihslovenia.si/aktualno/dogodki/vabilo-na-mednarodni-dogodek-underpin-road-show-maribor
17	13.5.25	Event	https://graphwise.ai/event/2nd-sm4rt-pin-deep-dive/
18	28.5.25	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.eu/news/details/tiko-pro-leads-the-way-in-hosting-underpins-general-assembly-and-road-show-in-maribor
19	4.6.2025	General News	https://www.tiko-pro.eu/news/details/tiko-pro-at-gitex-europe-2025-in-berlin

ANNEX V

Partner social media activity

No	BEN	Date	Social media	Link to the post
1	MOH	1.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpin-project-data-space-for-manufacturing-activity-7158756675716354048_kEp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
2	TP	6.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7160655011348201474
3	WM	9.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7161727339712782336/
4	WM	9.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7161727339712782336/
5	OT	9.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.ontotext.com/company/news/ontotext-joins-the-underpin-project/
6	TP	12.2.24	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/tikoprohr/posts/pfbid0kyaqpoRFYbiZn269VSTJrbXxcoJVpSdpgnM6k8qp4o25NU5Bpv6SxauyeDXhx1AMI?locale=hr_HR
7	TP	12.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7162819514059898880
8	TP	12.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-underpin-digitaleurope-underpinproject-activity-7162764791743201280-kG6Z?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
9	TP	12.2.24	Facebook	https://web.facebook.com/tikopro.si/posts/pfbid02EE5q5vaGjfc5AuoECdCceNjv2KB9vXMrUSzuwkE6jf93qqL96KkZACAV6G3BNvD1!
10	WM	26.2.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/w-melon_underpinproject-underpindataspace-dataspaceessymposium-activity-7167853135745433600-SFJU/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
11	MOH	8.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7183077479291437056/?actorCompanyId=101264383
12	INNOV	14.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ddrak_dataspaceessymposium-darmstadt-dataspace-activity-7173612549303648257-D3bO?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
13	MOH	28.3.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_dataspace-manufacturing-predictivemaintenance-activity-7176866194933637121-YN6k?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
14	TP	1.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_digital-europe-activity-7177929720452300800-fFF?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
15	TP	2.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7180850750917402624
16	TP	2.4.24	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=944262641032833&set=a.356638316461938
17	TP	5.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181976716213424130
18	TP	5.4.24	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=824395576372838&set=a.436856145126785
19	TP	12.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7184531851561095168

20	TP	12.4.24	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/tikoprohr/posts/pfbid0pyaLVaqAhCSJnquBZtbXwGHm857j7ixDeng6QXp9MFCJzC8dipo3dpSiKhzXjaMMI?locale=hr_HR
21	OT	15.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/valexiev_refinery-activity-7184917407642050560-hEo?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
22	TP	16.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_refineries-underpinproject-digitaltransformation-activity-7186611959830638592-89Xm?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
23	TP	22.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_underpinproject-dataspace-semanticweb-activity-7189148691847331840-rBcG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
24	TP	24.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_underpinproject-dataspace-semanticweb-activity-7189148691847331840-rBcG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
25	TP	29.4.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_project-partners-tiko-pro-activity-7189306222729183234-HRet?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
26	TP	6.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-_what-are-data-spaces-activity-7212386792660955137-rmZ3?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
27	TP	8.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kristina-ko%C4%8Det-hudrap-92930111_watermelonconsulting-underpinproject-energyinnovation-activity-7193859753167478784-0XMj?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
28	MORE	20.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpinproject-underpindataspace-innovation-activity-7197211184243044353-GTuq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
29	WM	29.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/w-melon_dataspace-manufacturing-underpinproject-activity-7201557409184624640-0ReC?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
30	MOH	30.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dataspace40_data-dataspace-dataspaces-activity-7202293975926345728-Qpcm?utm_source=combined_share_message&utm_medium=member_desktop_web
31	WM	31.5.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/w-melon_dataspace-manufacturing-refineries-activity-7202293012960362497-76rt?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
32	HUA	1.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_underpinproject-underpindataspace-innovation-activity-7197927705584041984-UCeB?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
33	TP	3.6.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-_underpindataspace-projectmanagement-eufunding-activity-7208425328556310528-UAm5?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
34	OT	6.6.24	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1798620589684380150
35	OT	17.6.24	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1802682098530058678
36	OT	27.6.24	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1806354960721785171
37	SWC	1.9.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/databri-x_swc-databrix-interoperability-activity-7250409291050811392-z5cH?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

38	OT	4.10.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7247174234202886145/
39	WM	15.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/w-melon_waterme%CE%BBon-consulting-had-the-privilege-of-activity-7263122057582759936-E6fh?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
40	OT	18.11.24	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1858417944427929673
41	OT	18.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264183657404264448
42	HUA	25.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_dataecosystem-sustainability-innovation-activity-7264299556018827264-2Uhn?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnABt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_jjs3Bsgx6bA
43	HUA	28.11.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_highlights-from-the-latest-event-on-data-activity-7271886238733766656-QAwP?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnABt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_jjs3Bsgx6bA
44	MOH	30.11.24	LinkedIn	Post Feed LinkedIn
45	MOH	22.12.24	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/motor-oil-hellas_underpinproject-manufacturing-underpindataspace-activity-7146415006706814977-XDLP?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
46	OT	10.2.25	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1888867093296144805
47	OT	10.2.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7294630677075927041
48	INNO V	1.3.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/innov-acts_from-idsa-standards-to-simpl-solutions-activity-7298350416545636353-LW0b?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
49	HUA	3.3.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_dataspaces-smartindustry-underpin-activity-7303307404211875840-rNxG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnABt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_jjs3Bsgx6bA
50	TP	13.3.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-hrvatska_euprojectsinsider-tikopro-underpin-activity-7305571942667870208-KDrS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
51	HUA	15.3.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_dataspaces-dss2025-activity-7305518782368628736-0FEV?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnABt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_jjs3Bsgx6bA
52	INNO V	1.4.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_dataspaces-underpin-manufacturing-activity-7302946077060571137-XGv?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
53	TP	24.4.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-euprojectsinsider-underpin-tikopro-activity-7321103153154650115-JzeX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
54	TP	24.4.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-hrvatska_euprojectsinsider-tikopro-underpindataspace-activity-7321130230008414208-

				v5EK?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
55	TP	24.4.25	LinkedIn	https://web.facebook.com/photo?fbid=1225670286232304&set=a.472093354923338
56	HUA	28.4.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_join-us-for-the-sm4rt-underpin-deep-dive-activity-7321062395945095169-KSoY?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnAbt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_jjs3Bsgx6bA
57	MOH	28.4.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aristotelis-ntafalias-179566193_underpin-flex4res-manufacturing-activity-7322515233091035136-egFM?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAC13e20BeTNcpEP0MtQ2AwdMO7lkiqbK5p0
58	INNO V	1.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_ai-predictivemaintenance-underpinproject-activity-7313802542872707072-Nq0j?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
59	INNO V	5.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpin-flex4res-manufacturing-activity-7322484729117585408-i42N?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
60	OT	8.5.25	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1920427488779350138
61	OT	8.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7326193150090219520/
62	OT	8.5.25	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1920427488779350138
63	OT	8.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ontotext-ad_manufacturing-activity-7327992003206508544-uphD/
64	TP	9.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-_manufacturing-activity-7326547903890518016-KM3a?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
65	TP	9.5.25	LinkedIn	https://web.facebook.com/photo?fbid=1101623165316743&set=a.436856145126785
66	OT	12.5.25	X	https://x.com/valexiev1/status/1921881419338383401
67	TP	14.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7328359970985406464
68	TP	16.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7329063468467163137
69	TP	16.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7329066836203933697
70	TP	16.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o-_zadnja-prilo%C5%BEnost-za-prijavo-ne-zamudite-activity-7329072932725452800-gsxC?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
71	TP	16.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-hrvatska_manufacturing-manufacturing-dataspace-activity-7329078392530665472-BQs7?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
72	TP	16.5.25	Facebook	https://web.facebook.com/photo?fbid=1245636904235642&set=a.472093354923338
73	TP	16.5.25	LinkedIn	https://web.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=1106293468183046&set=a.436856145126785

74	TP	21.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330875546899312640
75	OT	22.5.25	X	https://x.com/ontotext/status/1925470190399009140
76	OT	22.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ontotext-ad_underpinproject-underpindataspace-activity-7331217285308661761-BQE0/
77	TP	22.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7331212236738265088
78	TP	22.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-d-o-o- euprojectsinsider-underpin-underpindataspace-activity-7331223561606459392-9OvS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
79	INNO V	26.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpinproject-sm4rtenance-dataspace-ugcPost-7330903231725748226-bl2 ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
80	WM	26.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7332732044554174464
81	INNO V	28.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/underpinproject_underpin-underpinproject-dataspace-ugcPost-7333430912581287936-ijua?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAJOFY8B87vh8tbhVQvTV4UPXZy6Bxk5z68
82	MOH	29.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7334123895551053824/
83	HUA	5.5.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/intelligent-computer-systems-and-applications-icsa_underpin-manufacturing-underpinproject-activity-7326553337544249344-zDSm?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAA4uMnABt7mWFMHcj_HlmC8_ajs3Bsgx6bA
84	WM	3.6.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335582613346107393
85	TP	4.6.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335924643045765120
86	TP	19.6.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7341374267663495171
87	TP	17.7.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tiko-pro-hrvatska_euprojectsinsider-underpin-underpindataspace-activity-7351522133648277504-nY5p?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAADM-s0BZUuHHqYqBvqNlc_sZha3AijbMZo
88	TP	17.9.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7351490868454785025
89	TP	14.8.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7361700396022542336
90	TP	20.8.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363848002203013121/?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_updateV2%3A%28urn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A7363848002203013121%2CFEED_DETAIL%2CEMPTY%2CDEFAULT%2Cfalse%29&actorCompanyId=10628212
91	TP	12.9.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7372216748038717440
92	TP	18.9.25	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7374342203197841408

ANNEX VI

Zeleno omrežje, Slovenija, July 2025

12 NOVICE ČLANOV ZELENEGA OMREŽJA / ESG 201 / julij 2025

odpadnega tekstila (KNOF) in večnega najlona iz odpadnega (AquaFil) ter skupnostnimi prostori, kot so Center Rog, mestna točka »Misije 100« in Knjižnica Reči, kjer si prebivalci delijo vse od vrtnega orodja do otroških iger, je dogodek spodbudil prenos znanj in dobrih praks za prehod na brezogljičnost.

RRA Ljubljanske urbane regije
www.rralur.si

Trajnostni turizem – prihodnost turizma v Sloveniji

 Univerza v Novem mestu
University of Nova mesto

 REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
MINISTRSTVO ZA VISOKO ŠOLSIVO,
ZNANOST IN INOVACIJE

 Sofinancira Evropska unija

Turizem je dejavnost, ki pomembno prispeva h gospodarski aktivnosti posamezne države, saj pomembno vpliva na bruto domači proizvod (BDP), zaposlovanje in razvoj. V Evropski uniji (EU) turistični sektor šteje 2,3 milijona podjetij, ki skupaj zaposlujejo okoli 12,3 milijona ljudi in prispevajo približno 10 % celotnega BDP. Turizem pa ima izjemni pomen tudi za Slovenijo. Čeprav je bilo v zadnjih letih veliko napora na področju turizma namenjenega okrevanju po pandemiji covid-19, je EU in s tem tudi Slovenija dajala velik poudarek tudi na trajnosti v turizmu. Torej odgovornemu turizmu, ki spoštuje potrebe okolja in ljudi, ki tam živijo, kakor tudi lokalnega gospodarstva in obiskovalcev. Slovenija, ki se ponosa z nazivom ene najbolj zelenih držav na svetu, je s svojo naravno lepoto, bogato kulturno dediščino in trajnostno usmerjenostjo postala ena izmed vodilnih destinacij za trajnostni turizem v Evropi. Kako se to uresničuje v praksi proučujejo študenti, ki sodelujejo na projektu PUS 2024–2027 (Problemsko učenje študentov v delovno

okolje: gospodarstvo, negospodarstvo in neprofitni sektor v lokalnem/regionalnem okolju 2024–2027) Univerze v Novem mestu z naslovom Trajnostni turizem – prihodnost turizma v Sloveniji, ki ga financirata Ministrstvo za visoko šolstvo, znanost in inovacije ter Evropski socialni sklad plus (ESS+). Vse bralce tako prosimo, da rešijo anketo, ki je dostopna tukaj <https://1ka.arnes.si/a/Ba20bf90> oz. QR

UNM Fakulteta za ekonomijo in informatiko
<https://uni-nm.si>

EU Projekt za trajnostno prihodnost v proizvodnji

 UNDERPIN

 Co-funded by the European Union

V času digitalne transformacije trajnost postaja ključna komponenta za evropske industrije. Projekt UNDERPIN, sofinanciran s strani EU, pivotira k digitalni preobrazbi v proizvodnem sektorju, z osredotočenostjo na trajnostne prakse in odločitve, ki temeljijo na podatkih. Z ustvarjanjem panevropskega podatkovnega prostora UNDERPIN poenostavlja operacije, izboljšuje učinkovitost in povečuje trajnost v industrijah. Projekt uporablja napredno tehnologijo za predvidljivo vzdrževanje, zmanjšanje nepričakovanih izpadov in optimizacijo virov. S tem preprečuje nepotreben odpadni material in tako zagotavlja bolj trajnostno proizvodnjo. UNDERPIN Data Space omogoča varno izmenjavo podatkov med proizvajalci, raziskovalnimi institucijami in drugimi deležniki, kar omogoča optimizacijo proizvodnih procesov, zmanjšanje odpadkov in podaljšanje življenjske dobe sredstev. Tiko Pro kot partner v projektu UNDERPIN zagotavlja podporo pri komunikaciji, diseminaciji. UNDERPIN je primer, kako digitalna transformacija in trajnost delujeta v sožitju za čistejšo in učinkovitejšo prihodnost. Vse

informacije o projektu so na voljo na www.underpinproject.eu.

Tiko Pro d.o.o.
www.tiko-pro.si

Multisensory Art

 FAKULTETA ZA DIZAJN
SAMOSTOJNI PEDAGOGSKI ZAVOD

 SVEUČILIŠTE U DUBROVNIKU
UNIVERSITY OF DUBROVNIK

 FAKULTET SAVREMENIH UMETNOSTI

 REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
MINISTRSTVO ZA JAVNO UPRAVO

 Sofinancira Evropska unija

Fakulteta za dizajn je nosilka evropskega projekta Multisensory Art, ki je namenjen izboljšanju dostopa do umetnosti za slepe in slabovidne. V okviru projekta, ki se bo izvajal v Sloveniji, Srbiji in na Hrvaškem bomo izvedli 12 dvodnevnih delavnic in 10 razstav namenjenih slepim in slabovidnim. Rdeča nit vseh dogodkov bo uporaba recikliranih materialov. Do sedaj smo v Sloveniji izvedli 4 dvodnevne delavnice. Na delavnicah z glino smo uporabili reciklirano glino, pesek ter orodja iz naravnih in recikliranih materialov. Na delavnicah z lesom smo uporabili stare bambusove podstavke za posodo, odpadni material, ki so ga donirali v tovarni Podgorje, star lamelni parket, plutovinaste zamaške, koščke naplavljenega lesa, geometrijske like, ki so ostanek laserskega izreza in so nam ga donirali v podjetju Česles. Na delavnici mozaika, pa so udeleženci uporabili odpisane vzorčne kose mozaikov iz trgovine s keramiko in podlage za mozaik v obliki starih okvirjev in krožnikov iz ljubljanskega Centra ponovne uporabe. Zapisali: prof. dr. Jasna Hrovatin, doc. Mojca Perše, viš. pred. Petra Kocjančič

Fakulteta za dizajn, samostojni visokošolski zavod
<https://fd.si/>

Domača stran / Zeleno omrežje /

EU Projekt za trajnostno prihodnost v proizvodnji

16. 07. 2025 / Revija ESG št. 201

V času digitalne transformacije trajnost postaja ključna komponenta za evropske industrije. Projekt UNDERPIN, sofinanciran s strani EU, pivoira k digitalni preobrazbi v proizvodnem sektorju, z osredotočenostjo na trajnostne pralse in odločitve, ki temeljijo na podatkih. Z ustvarjanjem panevropskega podatkovnega prostora UNDERPIN poenostavlja operacije, izboljšuje učinkovitost in povečuje trajnost v industrijah. Projekt uporablja napredno tehnologijo za predvidljivo vzdrževanje, zmanjšanje nepričakovanih izpadov in optimizacijo virov. S tem preprečuje nepotreben odpadni material in tako zagotavlja bolj trajnostno proizvodnjo. UNDERPIN Data Space omogoča varno izmenjavo podatkov med proizvajalci, raziskovalnimi institucijami in drugimi deležniki, kar omogoča optimizacijo proizvodnih procesov, zmanjšanje odpadkov in podaljšanje življenjske dobe sredstev. Tiko Pro kot partner v projektu UNDERPIN zagotavlja podporo pri komunikaciji, diseminaciji. UNDERPIN je primer, kako digitalna transformacija in trajnost delujeta v sožitju za čistejšo in učinkovitejšo prihodnost. Vse informacije o projektu so na voljo na www.underpinproject.eu.

 Tiko Pro d.o.o.
www.tiko-pro.si

ANNEX VII

Data Spaces Radar Report, March, 2024

UNDERPIN

Data space for manufacturing excellence

Scan for more info

Challenge

Current data handling methods hinder industrial data use due to data silos and security issues while data sharing data across systems adds security risks. Specialized infrastructures are needed to unlock the full potential of this data, enabling new services, and boosting Industry 4.0 adoption. Medium-sized companies face additional challenges like labour-intensive data integration and lack of standardization. Overcoming data sovereignty concerns is crucial for widespread Industry 4.0 adoption, particularly in the data-driven European economy.

Success

UNDERPIN's mission is to develop an advanced platform for dynamic asset management and predictive/prescriptive maintenance. The UNDERPIN data space promotes cross-organizational data sharing while prioritizing data sovereignty. By fostering collaboration between SMEs and large industry players, the initiative aims to drive innovation and efficiency in the industry. Our solution includes interoperable data spaces, AI tools, FAIR datasets, and involvement from various stakeholders to optimize asset management processes. Tailored for European manufacturers in the refinery and renewable energy sectors, UNDERPIN is set to revolutionize data-driven solutions.

+ Benefits

- » *Improving processes, cost structure and material management via beyond the state-of-the-art data analysis.*
- » *Ensuring higher performance, better insight on asset critically, reduced overall downtimes and maintenance costs, extended machine usage periods, improved future machine designs, new service models, improve production line operations, company-internal processes, increased usability.*
- » *Enhancing business opportunities for industrial data value added services, supporting the transition towards circular economy.*

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101123179.

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ANNEX VIII

IDSA Ecosystem Building Call, 30 September, 2024

Today's Agenda

What do we want to talk about today?

- Introduction
- Industrial Data Spaces in Manufacturing: The UNDERPIN Project
- Q&A and Discussion
- Updates and Upcoming Events

2 Deep-dive presentations

- **Industrial Data Spaces in Manufacturing: The UNDERPIN Project**

(Aristotelis Antafalias, MOH & Sebastian Kleff, Sovity)

- The **UNDERPIN Project**, led by **Motor Oil Hellas (MOH)**, is addressing critical challenges in the manufacturing sector, including process optimization, product lifecycle management, and data silos that hinder effective cross-organizational data sharing. MOH, a major energy player based in Greece, leads the project with a focus on two main use cases: **refinery maintenance** and **wind farm management**. The **refinery use case** is geared toward improving operational efficiency by streamlining maintenance processes and enhancing decision-making through new predictive models that rely on historical data. Meanwhile, the **wind farm use case** focuses on preventing costly mechanical failures and optimizing turbine performance by utilizing meteorological, sensor, and failure data from various wind turbine manufacturers.
- One of the project's key differentiators is its emphasis on **cross-sectoral collaboration**, aiming to break down data silos and encourage eco-friendly practices in the manufacturing industry. The project aims to drive **data-driven innovation** by involving both **SMEs** and large enterprises, and it has already deployed its **first MVP**.
- **Sovity**, a technical partner in the project, demonstrated the **Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS)**. This live demo showcased the architecture of the data space, which includes essential components like connectors, identity providers, a marketplace, digital twin registry, and a customer portal. Sovity's data space solution plays a pivotal role in enabling the interoperability needed for seamless data sharing. They are involved in multiple other initiatives, including **Catena-X** and **Omega-X**, and their contribution ensures that **UNDERPIN** benefits from robust technical expertise and cutting-edge tools for secure and efficient data exchange.
- Currently, **UNDERPIN** is focused on rolling out five data connectors to allow data sharing between its partners. The goal is to engage key stakeholders in the active use of this data

www.internationaldataspaces.org

// =

space, pushing the project from its MVP phase into full operation. Some of the challenges they face include securing more participants, establishing a clearer value proposition for industry stakeholders, and ensuring data harmonization across different companies and sectors.

- The project has yielded valuable **lessons learned**, such as the benefits of early MVP deployment, leveraging existing knowledge from other data space initiatives, and the realization that there are no major technical obstacles so far. The next steps for the project involve developing a **credit scheme for data sharing**, finalizing the deployment of connectors, and bringing more industry players and SMEs into the fold.
- The **UNDERPIN** project team will participate in significant industry events, such as the **European Big Data Value Forum** in Budapest and the **Global Data Spaces Connect** in Vienna, providing an opportunity for further engagement and discussions on data sharing and its impact on the manufacturing industry.

3 Q&A/Discussion

- During the discussion, NTT suggested that offering a hands-on environment for IDSA members, using Sovity's services, could enhance understanding of data spaces. IDSA then asked about MOH's plans to engage companies. MOH explained that they aim to encourage companies to share data and collaborate in creating value through the data space. They plan to showcase their MVP at industry events to attract stakeholders. IDSA inquired about relationships with Manufacturing-X, to which MOH responded that, while they haven't established ties yet, they plan to.
- The importance of sustaining the project beyond its initial funding was emphasized. Engineering raised questions about data forms and management, and MOH discussed their efforts to develop a curation service for cleaning and preparing data, acknowledging ongoing work on automating data sharing. They expect to have more updates in six months once their data connectors are fully deployed.

ANNEX IX

Road Show Maribor announcement, May, 2025

HOME KONTAKT PRESSE NEWSLETTER MITGLIEDERBEREICH

INDUSTRIE 4.0
 10 JAHRE ÖSTERREICH

ÜBER DIE PLATTFORM THEMENSCHWERPUNKTE PROJEKTE AKTUELLES VERANSTALTUNGEN MITGLIED WERDEN

UNDERPIN ROAD SHOW – DISCOVER THE FUTURE OF DATA SPACES IN MANUFACTURING

2025-05-22 17:30 - 20:00

<https://esma.tiko-pro.si/underpin-road-show>

Hotel Habakuk (Diplomatic club)

Address: Maribor, Slowenien

Einblicke in das UNDERPIN Projekt zum Aufbau eines Produktions-Datenraums

Detaillierte Agenda und Anmeldung [auf der Event-Webseite](#)

ANNEX X

Tiko Pro news, May, 2025

Tiko Pro gostil generalno skupščino in Road Show dogodek projekta UNDERPIN v Mariboru

Projekt UNDERPIN semo zasevno skupščino in drugi Road Show
 Date: 28. 05. 2025

Pretekli teden je Maribor postal središče evropskih inovacij na področju podatkovnih prostorov, saj je Tiko Pro z velikim ponosom gostil 3. generalno skupščino mednarodnega projekta UNDERPIN, ki ji je sledil Road Show dogodek, namenjen povezovanju z regionalno proizvodno skupnostjo.

Dvodnevno srečanje, ki je potekalo v mariborskem Hotelu Habakuk, je združilo predstavnike vseh desetih partnerskih organizacij v konzorciju. Kot organizator je Tiko Pro zagotovil odlično koordinacijo in spodbudno okolje za delo, s čimer smo znova potrdili svojo vlogo zanesljivega partnerja na področju upravljanja EU projektov, strateškega komuniciranja in vključevanja deležnikov.

Generalna skupščina je potrdila, da projekt UNDERPIN napreduje po načrtih in je na dobri poti, da projekt uspešno zaključi v novembru 2025. Partnerji so dosegli pomemben napredek pri vzpostavljanju panevropskega podatkovnega prostora za proizvodnjo – ciljno usmerjenega v varno povezovanje proizvajalcev, energetskih podjetij in MSP-jev, podporo modelom za prediktivno vzdrževanje ter odklepanje novih poslovnih modelov, s temlejem na deljenju industrijskih podatkov.

Projekt s konkretnimi učinki in vse večjo prepoznavnostjo

Med internimi delovnimi srečanjmi so partnerji izpostavili konkretne rezultate projekta ter vse večjo prepoznavnost, ki jo projekt pridobiva na evropski ravni – preko strokovnih publikacij, mednarodnih dogodkov in strateških partnerstev. Pod vodstvom Tiko Pro na področju komuniciranja in diseminacije se je vidnost projekta močno povečala, kar prispeva k resničnemu vplivu v industriji.

Road Show: regionalno povezovanje in priložnosti za MSP-je

22. maja je Road Show dogodek odprl vrata malim in srednje velikim proizvodnim podjetjem ter deležnikom iz Slovenije, Hrvaške in Avstrije. Mednarodni projektni partnerji – med njimi Motor Oil Group, MORE, Heraklepo University, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology in Ontotext – so predstavili konkretne primere, kako podatkovni prostori omogočajo zmanjševanje izpadov, vzpostavljanje modelov »data-as-a-service« ter gradnjo vključujočega, podatkovno vodenega industrijskega ekosistema.

Dogodek je spodbudil živahno razpravo in potrdil dvojnjo realnost – izjemne priložnosti na eni strani ter vrzel v ozaveščenosti na drugi. Tiko Pro kot zanesljiv partner v projektu UNDERPIN ostaja predan zmanjševanju te vrzeli – z aktivno podporo MSP-jem pri razumevanju, vključevanju in izkoriščanju pobud evropskih podatkovnih prostorov.

Pogled naprej: moč sodelovanja

Uspehi dogodka je odprl nova vrata sodelovanja. Veseli nas, da smo gostil številne MSP-je, ki so izrazila zanimanje za sodelovanje in prihodnjih projektih programa Digitalna Evropa. Za mnoge je bil to prvi stik s konceptom industrijskih podatkovnih prostorov in njihovim potencialom.

V Tiko Pro se zavežujemo k temu, da kompleksne EU pobude pretvorimo v jasne, izvedljive strategije. Ne glede na to, ali gre za pripravo projektnih prijev, vključevanje deležnikov ali vodenje komunikacijskih aktivnosti – tu smo, da podjetjem pomagamo odpreti vrata v svet evropskih sredstev in inovacij.

Projekt UNDERPIN vstopa v svojo zaključno fazo, pred nami pa so novi Road Show dogodki, poglobljena sodelovanja in še več priložnosti za podjetja, da postanejo del digitalne preobrazbe Evrope.

Kontaktirajte nas: www.tiko-pro.eu/contact-us
 Več o projektu UNDERPIN: underpinproject.eu

ANNEX XI

Road Show Maribor, Digital Innovation Hub Slovenia, May 2025

DIGITALNO INOVACIJSKO STIČIŠČE SLOVENIJE

Aktualno ▾
Projekti
Strokovnjaki ▾
Orodja ▾
Baza znanja ▾
O nas ▾

← Nazaj na: Dogodki

22.
 maj
 17:30 - 19:00

Vabilo na mednarodni dogodek: UNDERPIN Road Show – Maribor

22. maj 2025
17:30 - 19:00

Hotel Habakuk (Diplomatski klub), Maribor
Pohorska ulica, Maribor

UNDERPIN
<https://esma.tiko-pro.si/underpin-road-show>

O dogodku in prijave

Prijavi se na dogodek →

V Mariboru bo 22. maja 2025 potekal mednarodni dogodek UNDERPIN Road Show, ki je namenjen predstavitvi evropskega projekta UNDERPIN in razvoju podatkovnega prostora za proizvodni sektor.

Namen dogodka je predstaviti napredek projekta in spodbuditi razpravo o priložnostih, izzivih ter prihodnjih korakih na področju podatkovnih prostorov v industriji.

Ključne vsebine dogodka:

- Predstavitve projekta UNDERPIN in vizije podatkovnega prostora za proizvodni sektor
- Pogovor o koristih in izzivih vzpostavljanja podatkovnih prostorov v praksi
- Primeri uporabe in možnosti sodelovanja v prihodnjih razvojnih fazah
- Mreženje z mednarodnimi partnerji iz Grčije, Cipra, Bolgarije, Avstrije in Slovenije

Dogodek bo potekal v Diplomatskem klubu Hotela Habakuk v Mariboru in bo odlična priložnost za izmenjavo znanja, povezovanje ter razmislek o prihodnosti digitalnega sodelovanja v industriji.

Prijava

Udeležba na dogodku je brezplačna, vendar je zaradi omejenega števila mest potrebna predhodna prijava.

Rok za prijavo: 15. maj 2025

ANNEX XII

Slovenian Business Club, February 2024

Tiko Pro kot ključni partner pri evropskem projektu za digitalizacijo industrije

ČLANI • 13. februar 2024

Podjetje Tiko Pro, član SBC - Kluba slovenskih podjetnikov sporoča, da se kot enakovreden partner pridružuje mednarodnemu konzorciju v prestižnem projektu Underpin, ki ga koordinira industrijski gigant Motor Oil iz Grčije.

Z več kot desetletno zgodovino uspešnega pridobivanja sredstev in z novim mejnikom v letu 2023, Tiko Pro krepi svojo vlogo na globalnem prizorišču digitalne inovacije.

Pri projektu sodeluje devet partnerjev iz štirih držav, in sicer Grčije, Avstrije, Slovenije in Cipra. Vodilni partner je Motor Oil Hellas, v konzorciju pa so poleg slovenskega podjetja Tiko Pro partnerji še Athena Research Center, Semantic Web Company, Watermelon, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, INNOV-ACTS, Space Hellas in Motor Oil Renewable Energy.

Projekt Underpin, financiran s strani programa Digital Europe, je zgled evropskega sodelovanja z vizijo ustvarjanja enotnega digitalnega trga. S projektom se vzpostavlja 'Data Space for Manufacturing', inovativni virtualni podatkovni prostor, namenjen prediktivni analitiki v proizvodnji.

Poudarek projekta je na povezovanju visokotehnoloških podatkovnih analiz s praktičnimi potrebami industrije, kar prispeva k večji učinkovitosti, zmanjšanju stroškov in spodbujanju trajnostnega razvoja.

V okviru projekta Underpin bodo postavljeni temelji za učinkovito uporabo industrijskih podatkov v realnem času. Motor Oil, kot koordinator projekta, bo skupaj z raziskovalnimi instituti in SME partnerji raziskoval in izvajal inovativne pristope k energetske učinkovitosti in zmanjšanju okoljskega vpliva. Projekt bo tako omogočil razvoj novih poslovnih modelov in vzpostavitev varnega okolja za izmenjavo podatkov, kjer bo vsak partner – ob upoštevanju trust agreementa – deloval v duhu zaupanja in skupnih ciljev.

Tiko Pro, kot enakovreden partner v konzorciju, prevzema vodilno vlogo pri diseminaciji in komunikaciji, kjer bo podjetje skrbelo za ozaveščanje ter vključevanje industrijskih podjetij v novonastali podatkovni prostor, s čimer se ustvarjajo predpogoji za pan-evropsko integracijo različnih industrijskih sektorjev. Ta integracija predstavlja pomemben korak k uresničevanju vizije Evropske unije o povezanem in digitalno naprednem gospodarstvu.

Cilj projekta je tudi spodbujanje tesnejšega sodelovanja med podatkovnimi lastniki in uporabniki, saj je skupna raba podatkov ključnega pomena za inovacije in optimizacijo poslovanja.

Projekt Underpin bo služil kot primer, kako lahko podjetja izkoristijo analitiko podatkov za optimizacijo svojih procesov in strojev, kar bo povečalo učinkovitost in znižalo stroške. "Predstavljajte si, da lahko z izboljšanjem proizvodnega procesa za samo pol sekunde ustvarite občutne prihranke," razlaga Kočet Hudrapova. "To je moč podatkovnih prostorov, ki jih razvijamo."

“

Vrednost projekta Underpin je 6.648.627 EUR, od česar je 4.050.375 EUR sofinanciranih s strani Evropske Unije. Tiko Pro je ponosen, da s svojim delom prispeva k uresničevanju ciljev tega ambicioznega projekta in potrjuje svojo zavezo k podpori evropskega gospodarstva na njegovi poti k digitalizaciji.

ANNEX XIII

Ontotext, Bulgaria, March, 2024

The screenshot shows a news article on the Ontotext website. The article title is "Ontotext Joins the UNDERPIN Project". The sub-headline reads: "The project contributes to the vision of the European Digital Single Market through the implementation of a European-wide Data Space for Manufacturing for dynamic asset management and predictive/prescriptive maintenance." The article is dated "5 Jun 2024" and is "2 min read". Below the text is a group photograph of the project team. The article body contains the following text:

In March 2024, Ontotext joined the [UNDERPIN project](#), a 24-month initiative funded by the European Union that addresses the vision of the European Digital Single Market. A consortium of 11 partners from 5 EU countries is working on a European-wide Data Space for Manufacturing for dynamic asset management and predictive/prescriptive maintenance.

The UNDERPIN consortium gathered on May 14-15, 2024 for its first General Assembly in Limassol, Cyprus. Many topics were discussed including use cases in critical manufacturing industries, namely oil refinery production and wind farms. Effort on these use cases involves developing beyond state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms for time-series analysis for the purposes of dynamic asset management. Pilot Digital Product Passports in these two critical industries will also be developed as part of the UNDERPIN project.

Another focus of the two-day assembly was the development of the UNDERPIN Data Space. Work on this has now commenced and a datathon on this topic will be held in late June in Vienna, organized by Semantic Web Company and the Austrian Institute of Technology.

Two more marathons will be held in the following months, one focusing on use cases and the other bringing together the results of the first two marathons. As Technical Lead of the project, Ontotext will be actively involved in all three.

Ontotext will also lead the work on Data Space Interoperability via Knowledge Graphs in order to facilitate the creation, use, transfer, and effective exchange of data across asset owners and other users of the data space. This interoperability is to be aligned with principles of governance, data sovereignty, and federation.

The UNDERPIN Data Space is meticulously crafted to be durable, secure, and fully compliant with data space and industry standards. SMEs, clusters, associations, international networks, and initiatives are all being recruited as key stakeholders of this European Manufacturing Data Space.

More great news and updates are on the way.

[Find out more about the UNDERPIN project.](#)

This project is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement No: 101123179. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not

ANNEX XIV

Road Show Vienna, DataBri-X, August, 2025

DataBri-X supports UNDERPIN Road Show in Vienna: Exploring Data Spaces and AI in Manufacturing

The **DataBri-X** project is proud to support the upcoming **UNDERPIN Road Show** event in Vienna, *Manufacturing Data Spaces: How Data Sharing & AI Support Manufacturing Excellence*. Taking place on **9 September 2025** from **16:00 to 19:30 CEST**, the event will bring together industry experts, innovators, and stakeholders to discuss how **data spaces** and **artificial intelligence** are transforming the manufacturing sector.

What to Expect:

- **Insights into Data Spaces** – Understanding their potential to revolutionise manufacturing.
- **AI-Powered Predictive Maintenance** – Improving asset management and operational efficiency.
- **Digital Product Passports (DPPs)** – Exploring their role and connection to data spaces.

This event offers a valuable opportunity to network with industry leaders, share knowledge, and explore potential collaborations that support innovation and sustainability in manufacturing.

ANNEX XV

Survey

 UNDERPIN survey

Thank you for participating in this survey. Your feedback is essential to the development of the UNDERPIN Data Space.

Please answer each question as accurately as possible to reflect your level of agreement or interest.

Completing the survey should take approximately five minutes.

*** Required**

1. What is your organisational status ? *

- Small medium enterprise (SME)
- Startup
- Large industry
- Business Support Organization
- Research Organization
- Public Authority
- Other

2. You are interested in sharing your data in a trustworthy environment like UNDERPIN. *

- Yes
- No

3. Have you ever shared data through digital platforms like Data Spaces or Marketplaces? *

- Yes
- No

4. If yes, what can be improved?

System Interoperability

Security

Data ownership control

Communication with data providers / consumers

Other

5. If you answered "Other" to the previous question, please clarify.

6. Which of the following do you consider as benefits for joining the UNDERPIN Data Space: *

7. If you answered "Other" to the previous question, please clarify.

8. Which role do you find appealing in joining UNDERPIN? *

Data provider

Data user

Service developer